

Compléments à l'article *Literatur* de D.O.Edzard, RIA 7, 1/2 (1987) 35-48 (choix)¹

Pascal Attinger, 2020

Adapa: A. Cavigneaux, ZA 104 (2014) 1-41; A. Annus, SAAS 24 (2016) 14-16 et 105-110. — Cf. S.J. Milstein, ZA 105 (2015) 30-41; ead., Tracking the Master Scribe: Revision through Introduction in Biblical and Mesopotamian Literature (2016) 76-109 passim.

Angim dimma (3.1.a): Bottéro/Kramer, Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme 377-389; ETCSL 1.6.1 (1998); G. Pettinato, Mitologia sumerica (2001) 235-246; Black et alii, LAS 181-186; Attinger/A. Glenn, TTS (2017). — Cf. Bruschweiler, Inanna 73 sq.; Wilcke, Politik und Literatur 60 sq.; Penglase, Greek Myths 55-60; M. Streck, Or. 71 (2002) 225-227; Wagensonner, Götterreisen (2005) 129-132; I. Vorontsov, NABU 2008/24; J.-D. Forest, Mém. Bottéro 45 sq.; 47-53 passim; L. Feldt, Mém. Black 69-92; M. Viano, The Reception of Sumerian Literature in the Western Periphery (2016) 43 sq. et 95-97; K. Wagensonner, dans:

¹¹ Non enregistrés ici sont les nouveaux duplicats et les comptes rendus des éditions. La date figurant après les renvois à ETCSL est celle de l'"editor: standardisation, proofreading, (adapting) translation", car les corrections postérieures sont de caractère mineur. J'ai fait une exception pour Gudam, qui mentionne des "major corrections". Les abréviations utilisées sont en général celles de P. Attinger, *Eléments de linguistique sumérienne*. [...] (Orbis Biblicus et Orientalis Sonderband, Fribourg Suisse/Göttingen, 1993); ajouter: Attinger, TTS = P. Attinger, Traductions de textes sumériens (<http://www.iaw.unibe.ch/atinger>); Black et alii, LAS = J. Black et alii, The Literature of Ancient Sumer (2004); Bottéro/Kramer, Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme = J. Bottéro/S.N. Kramer, Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme. [...], Paris, 1989; Broekema, Inanna = H. Broekema, Inanna, heerseres van hemel en aarde [...] (2013); Clifford, Creation Accounts = R.J. Clifford, Creation Accounts in the Ancient Near East and in the Bible (= The Catholic Biblical Quarterly Monograph Series 26, 1994); Delnero, Variation = P. Delnero, Variation in Sumerian Literary Compositions: A Case Study Based on the Decad. Ph. D., Univ. of Pennsylvania 2006; Gadotti, The feminine in myths and epic = A. Gadotti, The feminine in myths and epic, in: M.W. Chavalas (ed.), Women in the ancient Near East, New York 2014, 28-58; Gadotti, Sumerian wisdom literature = A. Gadotti, Sumerian wisdom literature, in: M.W. Chavalas (ed.), Women in the ancient Near East, New York 2014, 59-74; Hruška, Ackerbau = B. Hruška, Tradiční obilnárství staré Mezopotámie [Der traditionelle Ackerbau im alten Mesopotamien], Prague, 1990; Jacobsen, The Harps that once... = Th. Jacobsen, The Harps that once ... [...], Yale, 1987; Kramer/Maier, Myths of Enki = S.N. Kramer/J. Maier, Myths of Enki, The Crafty God, New York/Oxford, 1989; Kramer/Molina, El Matrimonio Sagrado = S.N. Kramer, El Matrimonio Sagrado en la Antigua Sumer. Traducción y adaptación de Manuel Molina (= Colección: Estudios Orientales 11, 1999); Leick, Sex and Eroticism = G. Leick, Sex and Eroticism in Mesopotamian Literature, London/New York, 1994; Lisman, At the beginning = J.J.W. Lisman, At the beginning... Cosmogony, theogony and anthropogony in Sumerian texts of the third and second millennium BCE. Ph. D. Diss., Universiteit Leiden 2013; Mém. Hallo = M.E. Cohen/D.C. Snell/D.B. Weisberg (ed.), The Tablet and the Scroll. Near Eastern Studies in Honor of WILLIAM W. HALLO, Bethesda, 1993; Mém. Black = H.D. Baker et al. (ed.), Your Praise is Sweet: A Memorial Volume for Jeremy Black from Students, Colleagues and Friends, London 2010; Mesopotamian Epic Literature = M.E. Vogelzang/H.L.J. Vanstiphout (ed.), Mesopotamian Epic Literature. Oral or Aural?, Lewiston, 1992; Penglase, Greek Myths = C. Penglase, Greek Myths and Mesopotamia [...], London/New York, 1994; Peterson, Faunal Conception = J. Peterson, A Study of Sumerian Faunal Conception with a Focus on the Terms Pertaining to the Order *Testudines*, Ph. D. Diss., Univ. of Pennsylvania 2007; Raphael Kutscher Memorial Volume = A.F. Rainey (ed.), *kinattūtu ša dārāti*: Raphael Kutscher Memorial Volume, Tel Aviv, 1993; Rollinger, Frühformen = R. Rollinger, Frühformen historischen Denkens [...] (dissertation non pub., Innsbruck, 1993); The Context of Scripture I = W.W. Hallo/K. Lawson Younger, Jr. (ed.), The Context of Scripture Vol. I: Canonical Compositions from the Biblical World, Leiden, Boston, Köln 1997; The Context of Scripture II = W.W. Hallo/K. Lawson Younger, Jr. (ed.), The Context of Scripture Vol. II: Monumental Inscriptions from the Biblical World, Leiden, Boston, Köln 2000; Vanstiphout, Eduba = H. Vanstiphout, Eduba. Schrijven en lezen in Sumer (2004); Wagensonner, Götterreisen = K. Wagensonner, "Wenn Götter reisen ...". Götterreisen, -prozessionen und Besuchsfahrten in den sumerischen literarischen Texten (Diplomarbeit zur Erlangung des Magistergrades der Philosophie aus der Studienrichtung Altsemitische Philologie und Orientalische Archäologie eingereicht an der Universität Wien, 2005). Wilcke, Anfänge = C. Wilcke, Vom altorientalischen Blick zurück auf die Anfänge, dans: E. Angehrn (ed.), Anfang und Ursprung. Die Frage nach dem Ersten in Philosophie und Kulturwissenschaft (Colloquium Rauricum 10, 2007) 3-59. Wilcke, Politik und Literatur = C. Wilcke, Politik und Literatur im älteren Babylonien, dans K. Raaflaub (ed.), Anfänge politischen Denkens in der Antike (= Schriften des Historischen Kollegs, Kolloquien 24, München, 1993) pp. 29-75.

J. Braarvig/M.J. Geller (ed.), *Multilingualism, Lingua Franca and Lingua Sacra* (Max Planck Research Library for the History and Development of Knowledge Studies 10, 2018) 256-261 et 282-284.

Dumuzis Tod (3.1.b): Jacobsen, *The Harps that once ...* 28-46; Bottéro/Kramer, *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme* 300-312; ETCSL 1.4.3 (1998); H. Vanstiphout, *Helden en goden van Sumer* (1998) 229-241; G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 492-507; Black et alii, *LAS* 77-84; Attinger, *TTS* (2009, actualisé en 2015); Attinger/J. Matuszak, dans K. Volk (ed.), *Erzählungen aus dem Land Sumer* (2015) 399-414 et 441. — Cf. W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT II/1* (1986) 27-30 (ll. 15-69); T. Kuwabara, *The Netherworld in Sumerian-Akkadian Literature* (Ph. D., Univ. of California at Berkeley, 1991) 43-52; A. da Silva, *BCSMS* 22 (1991) 31-35; Kramer/Molina, *El Matrimonio Sagrado* 142-150; M.M. Fritz, *AOAT* 307 (2003) 97-102; D. Katz, *The Image of the Netherworld in the Sumerian Sources* (2003) *passim*, surtout 301-308 (index des lignes discutées pp. 479 sq.); C. Hoffmann, *Dumuzi's Dream: Dream Analysis in Ancient Mesopotamia*, *Dreaming* 14 (2004) 240-251 (DuDr.: 240-247); P. Mander, *Canti sumerici d'amore e morte* (*Testi del Vicino Oriente antico* 2/8, 2005) 165-174 (traduction partielle); B. Alster, *ZA* 96 (2006) 1-30 (v. à ce propos P. Attinger, *NABU* 2006/69); Broekema, *Inanna* (2013) 311-315; Gadotti, *The feminine in myths and epic* (2014) 43-45, 54; M. Ceccarelli, *Fabula* 60 (2019) 114-117; C. Saporetti, *I sogni degli antichi. La Mesopotamia e i popoli vicini* (2019) 133-137.

Enki und Ninhursanga (3.1.c): Jacobsen, *The Harps that once ...* 181-204; Bottéro/Kramer, *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme* 151-164; W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT III/3* (1993) 363-386; ETCSL 1.1.1 (1998); H. Vanstiphout, *Helden en goden van Sumer* (1998) 150-164; G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 155-170; P. Attinger, dans P. Jovanovic, *Le Mensonge Universel* (Paris: Le jardin des Livres 2007) 55-72; Attinger, *TTS* (2011, actualisé en 2015); R. Jiménez Zamudio, *Isimu* 16 (2013) 13-38; T. Rodin, *The World of the Sumerian Mother Goddess: An Interpretation of Her Myths* (2014) 46-48, 111 sq., 115-228, 329-337 (trad.); Attinger, dans K. Volk (ed.), *Erzählungen aus dem Land Sumer* (2015) 5-20 et 417. — Cf. R.S. Falkowitz, *Entretiens sur l'antiquité classique* 30 (1984) 15-18; Vanstiphout, *CRRAI* 33 (1986, ed. 1987) 166 sq.; H. Limet, dans F. Jouan et B. Deforge (ed.), *Peuples et pays mythiques. Actes du V^e Colloque du Centre de Recherches mythologiques de l'Université de Paris X (Chantilly, 18-20 septembre 1986)* (1988) 11-19; Kramer/Maier, *Myths of Enki* 22-30; H. Limet, *Mél. Sjöberg* 357-360 et 364; Vanstiphout, *NABU* 1990/57; B.F. Batto, dans: K.L. Younger et alii (ed.), *The Biblical Canon in Comparative Perspective. Scripture in Context IV* (1991) 33-66; G. Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 76 et 318 sq.; T. Frymer-Kensky, *In the Wake of the Goddesses* (1992) 22 sq. et 72; C. Saporetti, *EVO* 16 (1993) 119 sq.; R.D. Wexler, *The Concepts of Mortality and Immortality in Ancient Mesopotamia* (Ph. D., Univ. of California 1993) 75-85 et 187-190; Leick, *Sex and Eroticism* 30-41 et 279 sq.; P. Michalowski in L. Milano (ed.), *Drinking in Ancient Societies* (Padoue, 1994) 41 sqq.; J.D. Evers, *AOAT* 241 (1995) 33-45; R.A. Casey, *Inanna and Enki in Sumer: an Ancient Conflict Revisited* (Ph. D., The California Institute of Integral Studies 1998) 157-190; Michalowski, *CRRAI* 43 (1998) 242 sq.; B. André-Salvini, dans: *Traces of Paradise: The Archaeology of Bahrain 2500 BC-3000 AD* (2000) 28-33; M. Stol, *CM* 14 (2000) 136 sq.; M.-F. Besnier, *CRRAI* 47 (2002) 60-64, 67, 69 sq.; M. Streck, *Or.* 71 (2002) 204-208; B. Lion, *Âges d'or et paradis perdus dans la littérature sumérienne*, dans: V. Pirenne-Delforge et Ö. Tunca (ed.), *Représentations du temps dans les religions. Actes du Colloque organisé par le Centre d'Histoire des Religions de l'Université de Liège* (2003) 56-59; M. Tanret, *Mél. Klener* (2004) 176-183; K. Dickson, *JAOS* 125 (2005) 499-515; Dickson, *JNES* 66 (2007) 1-

32; D. Katz, *BiOr.* 64 (2007) 568-589; ead., *BiOr.* 65 (2008) 320-342; P. Attinger, *NABU* 2008/71; L. Bachelot, *Mém. Bottéro* (2009) 36-39; B. Gadotti, *JAOS* 129 (2009) 74-76; N. Postgate, *Mém. Black* 237-243.; J. Scurlock, *NABU* 2010/31; C. Wilcke, dans: P. Gemeinhardt und A. Zgoll (ed.), *Weltkonstruktionen (Orientalische Religionen in der Antike* 5, 2010) 9-13; V. Grandpierre, *Sexe et amour de Sumer à Babylone* (2012) 32-40; P. Espak, dans: T. Kulmar und R. Schmitt (ed.), *Ideas of Man in the Conceptions of the Religions* (2012) 61-63; B.F. Batto, *In the Beginning: Essays on Creation Motifs in the Ancient Near East and the Bible* (2013) 56-65; Y.S. Chen, *The Primeval Flood Catastrophe [...]* (2013) 80-83; M. Guichard/L. Marti, dans: C. Frevel/C. Nihan (ed.), *Purity and the Forming of Religious Traditions in the Ancient Mediterranean World and Ancient Judaism* (2013) 60-65; A.-C. Rendu Loisel, *Heurs et malheurs du jardinier dans la littérature sumérienne*, dans: D. Barbu et al. (ed.), *Mondes clos, cultures et jardins* (2013) 68-72, 79 sq. et 337-340; Gadotti, *The feminine in myths and epic* (2014) 37-40, 50; J.C. Johnson, *BBVO* 23 (2014) 11-55 passim; G. Marchesi, *Kaskal* 11 (2014) 47-56; P. Espak, *The God Enki in Sumerian Royal Ideology and Mythology* (2015) 181-186; U. Steinert, dans: J.Z. Wee (ed.), *The comparable body: analogy and metaphor in ancient Mesopotamian, Egyptian, and Greco-Roman medicine (Studies in Ancient Medicine 49, 2017) 275-357 (Enki et Ninhursaga: pp. 314-316)*; N.W. Visser, *Enki's omzwervingen*, 2017; Ll. Feliu, dans: J.J. Justel and A. Garcia-Ventura (ed.), *Las mujeres en el Oriente cuneiforme* (2018) 124-126; L.M. Pryke, dans: K.H. Keimer/G. Davis (ed.), *Register and Modes of Communication in the Ancient Near East [...]* (2018) 214, 216; N.W. Visser, *ENKI and NINHURSAG: a REHABILITATION*, 2018 (résumé de Visser 2017, téléchargeable à l'adresse http://enki-and-ninhursag.com/en_US/); B. Böck, *Medicina nei Secoli* 30 (2018) 505-530; M. Ceravolo, *Historia Religionum* (2019) 119-137; R.M. van Dijk-Coombes, *Scriptura* 119 (2020) 4-6.

Enki und Ninmah (3.1.d): Jacobsen, *The Harps that once ...* 151-166; Bottéro/Kramer, *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme* 188-198; W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT III/3* (1993) 386-401; *ETCSL* 1.1.2 (1998); G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 407-415 (cf. aussi 117 sq.); W.G. Lambert, *MC* 16 (2013) 330-345, 498-509 et pl. 57-63 (édition); T. Rodin, *The World of the Sumerian Mother Goddess: An Interpretation of Her Myths* (2014) 44-46, 48-50, 111 sq., 229-298, 338-342 (trad.); M. Ceccarelli, *Enki und Ninmah. Eine mythische Erzählung in sumerischer Sprache (= ORA 16, 2016) (édition)*. — Cf. A. Draffkorn Kilmer, *AOAT* 25 (1976) 265-270; M.-J. Seux, dans Seux et al., *La création et le déluge d'après les textes du Proche-Orient ancien (Supplément au Cahier Evangile 64 [1988])* 24-26; I.M. Kikawada, *Iraq* 45 (1983) 43-45 (réédité dans R.S. Hess/D.T. Tsumura [ed.], *I Studied Inscriptions from Before the Flood [= Sources for Biblical and Theological Study 4, Winona Lake, 1994]* 169-174); R. Borger, *Or.* 54 (1985) 18-22; Kramer/Maier, *Myths of Enki* 31-37; H. Limet, *Mél. Sjöberg* 360 sq. et 364; G. Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 322 sq.; W.G. Lambert, *CRRAI* 38 (1991, ed. 1992) 129-135; T. Frymer-Kensky, *In the Wake of the Goddesses* (1992) 72 sqq.; H. Sauren, *Mél. Hallo* 198-208; C. Saporetti, *EVO* 16 (1993) 120 sq.; Leick, *Sex and Eroticism* 26-29 et 278 sq.; P. Michalowski in L. Milano (ed.), *Drinking in Ancient Societies (Padoue, 1994)* 41 sqq.; M. Dietrich, *AOAT* 240 (1995) 58-60; W. Heimpel, *RIA* 8/7-8 (1997) 558; J. Klein, *The Context of Scripture I* 516-518 (traduction partielle); R.A. Casey, *Inanna and Enki in Sumer: an Ancient Conflict Revisited (Ph. D., The California Institute of Integral Studies 1998)* 191-211; M. Stol, *CM* 14 (2000) 80/82 et 109 sq.; M. Streck, *Or.* 71 (2002) 197 sq.; M. Dietrich, *MARG* 16 (2004) 24-26; id., *MARG* 17 (2005) 141-144; Wilcke, *Anfänge* (2007) 29-34; A. Westenholz, *Mél. J.G. Westenholz* (2010) 201-204; P. Espak, dans: T. Kulmar und R. Schmitt (ed.), *Ideas of Man in the Conceptions of the*

Religions (2012) 46 sq., 54-56; U. Steinert, CM 44 (2012) 50 sq.; A. Zgoll, in: K. Schmid (ed.), *Schöpfung (= Themen der Theologie 4, 2012) 46-49*; J.M. Asher-Greve, OBO 259 (2013) 141-145; Y.S. Chen, *The Primeval Flood Catastrophe [...] (2013) 83-85*; Lisman, *At the beginning (2013) 46-50 et 268-283 = AOAT 409 (2013) 48-53 et 293-309*; Gadotti, *The feminine in myths and epic (2014) 40-43, 53 sq.*; P. Espak, *The God Enki in Sumerian Royal Ideology and Mythology (2015) 162-164 et 174 sq.*; S. Pittl, *Kaskal 12 (2015) 467-483*; Kaĝnici, G., *Tarih İncelemeri Dergisi 33 (2018) 429-450*; I. Peled, *AOAT 435 (2016) 84 sq.*, L. Verderame, *Mél. Geller (2018) 797 sq.*; C. Mittermayer, *UAVA 15 (2019) 12*; G. Matini/C. Sapoterri, *dubsar 6 (2019) 173-179*; L. Verderame, *Henoch 41 (2019) 21 sq.*

Enki und die Weltordnung (3.1.e): Bottéro/Kramer, *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme 165-188*; ETCSL 1.1.3 (1998); H. Vanstiphout, *Helden en goden van Sumer (1998) 184-203*; Vanstiphout, *Revue belge de philologie et d'histoire 77 (1999) 5-51 (édition)*; G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica (2001) 121-145*; Black et alii, *LAS 215-225*; R.E. Averbeck, dans: K. Lawson Younger Jr. (ed.), *The Context of Scripture IV (2017) 340-351*. — Cf. H. Limet, dans H. Limet/J. Ries (ed.) *Le mythe, son langage et son message (Actes du colloque de Liège et Louvain-la-Neuve, 1981; ed. dans Homo Religiosus 9, 1983) 81-96*; R.S. Falkowitz, *Entretiens sur l'antiquité classique 30 (1984) 13 sqq.*; Kramer/Maier, *Myths of Enki 38-56*; G. Pettinato, *I Sumeri (1991) 319-321*; W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT III/3 (1993) 402-420*; Wilcke, *Politik und Literatur 39-44*; Leick, *Sex and Eroticism 23-26 et 278*; H.L.J. Vanstiphout, *CM 7 (1997) 117-134*; R.A. Casey, *Inanna and Enki in Sumer: an Ancient Conflict Revisited (Ph. D., The California Institute of Integral Studies 1998) 128-156*; Kramer/Molina, *El Matrimonio Sagrado 64-66*; M. Stol, *CM 14 (2000) 110-112*; M. Streck, *Or. 71 (2002) 220*; R.E. Averbeck, in: R.E. Averbeck/alii, *Life and Culture in the Ancient Near East (2003) 26-61*; id., *JAOS 123 (2003) 757-771*; M. Tanret, *Mél. Klener (2004) 183-186*; K. Dickson, *JAOS 125 (2005) 502-504*; A.M. Bagg, *Schriften der DWhG 12 (2008) 216-218*; Y.S. Chen, *The Primeval Flood Catastrophe [...] (2013) 79*; C. Mittermayer, *OBO 256 (2012) 243-258*; I. Slobodzianek, *Acquérir, exprimer et transmettre les "pouvoirs" divins: une comparaison entre Aphrodite et Inanna/Ištar, thèse de doctorat, Toulouse 2012 (<https://de.scribd.com/document/135631970/Acquerir-exprimer-et-transmettre-les-pouvoirs-divins-Une-comparaison-entre-Aphrodite-et-Inanna-Istar>) 134-145*; P. Espak, *The God Enki in Sumerian Royal Ideology and Mythology (2015) 97-99*; E.S. Gerstenberger, *Theologie des Lobens in sumerischen Hymnen (= ORA 28, 2018) 194-200*; P. Espak, *Studia Orientalia Tartuensia 2019 37-42*; A.M. Bagg, *dubsar 17 (2020) 16 sq.*

Enlil und Ninlil (3.1.f): J.S. Cooper, *JCS 32 (1980) 175-188*; Jacobsen, *The Harps that once ... 167-180*; Bottéro/ Kramer, *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme 105-115*; W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT III/3 (1993) 421-434*; ETCSL 1.2.1 (1998); H. Vanstiphout, *Helden en goden van Sumer (1998) 165-173*; G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica (2001) 171-179*; J. Scurlock, *Nin 4 (2003 [paru en 2006]) 61-103 (traduction commentée aux pp. 62-65)*; Black et alii, *LAS 102-106*; Attinger, *TTS 2015*; H. Steible, dans K. Volk (ed.), *Erzählungen aus dem Land Sumer (2015) 21-31 et 417*. — Cf. A. Falkenstein, *ZA 47 (1942) 194-197*; S.N. Kramer, *Sumerian Mythology [...] (1944, 1961) 43-47 et 114*; T. Jacobsen, *JNES 4 (1946) 130 sq. n. 8, 132-134*; Kramer, *The Sumerians: Their History, Culture, and Character (1963) 146 sq.*; G.S. Kirk, *Myth: Its Meaning and Functions in Ancient and Other Cultures (1970) 99-103*; V. Afanasieva, *ZA 70 (1980) 163-169*; R.S. Falkowitz, *Entretiens sur l'antiquité classique 30 (1984) 18 sqq.*; Hall, *Nanna/Suen 524-526 et 609 sq.*; T. Kuwabara, *The Netherworld in Sumero-Akkadian Literature (Ph. D., Univ. of California at Berkeley, 1991)*

37-43; G. Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 316 sq.; Wilcke, *Politik und Literatur* 37 sq.; Leick, *Sex and Eroticism* 42-47 et 280 sq.; J.D. Evers, *AOAT* 241 (1995) 47-63; Michalowski, *CRRAI* 43 (1998) 243 sq.; Cooper, *CRRRA* 45/I (2001) 140 n. 44; J. Klein, *CRRAI* 45/I 283 sq.; M. Streck, *Or.* 71 (2002) 203 sq.; D. Katz, *The Image of the Netherworld in the Sumerian Sources* (2003) 37-39; B. Groneberg, *Die Götter des Zweistromlandes* (2004) 63-65 et 229 sq.; V. Van der Stede, *Lettres orientales* 12 (2007) 144 sq.; L. Bachelot, *Mém. Bottéro* (2009) 32-35; A. Gadotti, *JAOS* 129 (2009) 78-82; V. Grandpierre, *Sexe et amour de Sumer à Babylone* (2012) 25-29; A. Zgoll, *Mém. Hruška* (2011) 287-299; J.L. Cooley, *Poetic Astronomy in the Ancient Near East [...]* (2013) 111-114; A. Zgoll, *Fundamente des Lebens. Vom Potential altorientalischer Mythen*, dans: A. Zgoll und R.G. Kratz (ed.), *Arbeit am Mythos* (2013) 79-107; J.M. Asher-Greve, *OBO* 259 (2013) 145-148; Y.S. Chen, *The Primeval Flood Catastrophe [...]* (2013) 87 sq.; Gadotti, *The feminine in myths and epic* (2014) 29-33, 51 sq.; T. Rodin, *The World of the Sumerian Mother Goddess: An Interpretation of Her Myths* (2014) 221-227; M. Viano, *The Reception of Sumerian Literature in the Western Periphery* (2016) 37-41; L.M. Pryke, *Ishtar: Gods and Heroes of the Ancient World* (2017) 95-97; Ll. Feliu, dans: J.J. Justel and A. Garcia-Ventura (ed.), *Las mujeres en el Oriente cuneiforme* (2018) 220 sq.; L.M. Pryke, dans: K.H. Keimer/G. Davis (ed.), *Register and Modes of Communication in the Ancient Near East [...]* (2018) 211 sq. et 215 sq.; M. Ceccarelli, *Fabula* 60 (2019) 111-113 (à propos des ll.10-33); C. Zgoll, *Tractatus mythologicus [...]* (= *Mythological Studies* 1 [2019]) 505-508, 537 sq., 542 sq.; A. Zgoll, *Durch Tod zur Macht, selbst über den Tod. [...]*, dans: A. Zgoll/C. Zgoll (ed.), *Mythische Sphärenwechsel. Methodisch neue Zugänge zu antiken Mythen in Orient und Okzident* (= *Mythological Studies* 2 [2020]) 91.

Enlil und Sud (3.1.g): Bottéro/Kramer, *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme* 115-127; H. Vanstiphout, *Helden en goden van Sumer* (1998) 174-183; *ETCSL* 1.2.2 (2000); G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 180-190; Black et alii, *LAS* 106-111; M. Fritz, dans: B. Heininger (ed.), *An den Schwellen des Lebens. Zur Geschlechterdifferenz in Ritualen des Übergangs* (2008) 76-82. — Cf. H.L.J. Vanstiphout, *CRRAI* 33 (1986, ed. 1987) 169 sq.; C. Wilcke, *ib.* 180-185; C. Saporetti, *EVO* 16 (1993) 117-119; P. Michalowski, *NABU* 1994/51; *id.*, *CRRAI* 43 (1998) 243 sq.; M. Streck, *Or.* 71 (2002) 216; B. Groneberg, *Die Götter des Zweistromlandes* (2004) 65-67; V. Grandpierre, *Sexe et amour de Sumer à Babylone* (2012) 30 sq.; J.M. Asher-Greve, *OBO* 259 (2013) 145-148; Gadotti, *The feminine in myths and epic* (2014) 29, 33-37, 52; Ll. Feliu, dans: J.J. Justel and A. Garcia-Ventura (ed.), *Las mujeres en el Oriente cuneiforme* (2018) 121-124; L.M. Pryke, dans: K.H. Keimer/G. Davis (ed.), *Register and Modes of Communication in the Ancient Near East [...]* (2018) 210 sq. et 214; C. Zgoll, *Tractatus mythologicus [...]* (= *Mythological Studies* 1 [2019]) 487-489.

Enmerkar und der 'Herr' (en) von Aratta (3.1.h): Jacobsen, *The Harps that once ...* 275-319; *ETCSL* 1.8.2.3 (1998); H. Vanstiphout, *Helden en goden van Sumer* (1998) 84-112; *id.*, *Epics of Sumerian Kings: The Matter of Aratta* (= *Writings from the Ancient World* 20, 2004) 49-96; P. Attinger, *TTS* 2015; C. Mittermayer, *Enmerkara und der Herr von Arata. Ein ungleicher Wettstreit* (= *OBO* 239, 2009) (édition); *ead.*, *TUAT NF* 8 (2015) 3-24; Mittermayer, dans K. Volk (ed.), *Erzählungen aus dem Land Sumer* (2015) 169-201 et 421. — Cf. O.R. Gurney, *AfO* 25 (1974/1977) 170 sq.; B. Alster, *BBVO* 2 (1983) 39-74, surtout 57 sq.; H.L.J. Vanstiphout, *Mél. Sjöberg* 515-524; C. Uehlinger, *OBO* 101 (1990) 409-429; B.F. Batto, dans: K.L. Younger et alii (ed.), *The Biblical Canon in Comparative Perspective. Scripture in Context IV* (1991) 42-45 et 48-50; G. Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 76 sq. et 146-

151; Gurney, NABU 1992/54; Th. Jacobsen dans M. Fishbane/*alii* (ed.), "Sha²arei Talmon". Studies in the Bible, Qumran, and the Ancient Near East Presented to Shemaryahu Talmon, Winona Lake, 1992, pp. 403-416; Vanstiphout, Mesopotamian Epic Literature 247-264; C. Zaccagnini, AoF 20 (1993) 34-42; Vanstiphout, RA 88 (1994) 135-154; id., OLP 26 (1995) 5-20; id., CM 6 (1996) 162; Jacobsen, The Context of Scripture I 547-550 (traduction partielle); J.-J. Glassner, Écrire à Sumer (2000) 27-44; J. Klein, Studi Cagni (2000) 563-584; M. Streck, Or. 71 (2002) 210-212; C. Wilcke, in: M. Brehl/K. Platt (ed.), Feindschaft (2003) 109-111; C. Schmidt, BaM 36 (2005) 54 sq.; G. Pettinato, Dal mare alla montagna dei cedri. Il poema sumerico di Enmerkar ed Ensuĝgiranna (2006) 42-47; I. Good, Invisible Exports in Aratta: Enmerkar and the Three Tasks, dans: C. Gillis and M.-L. B. Nosch (ed.). Ancient Textiles: Production, Craft and Society. Proceedings of the First International Conference on Ancient Textiles, held at Lund, Sweden, and Copenhagen, Denmark, on March 9-23, 2003, Oxbow Books 2007, 179-184; Wilcke, Anfänge (2007) 24-26/47-49; J. Keetman, NABU 2010/63; id., ZA 100 (2010) 16-25; C. Mittermayer, CRRAI 53/1 (2010) 377-387; B.F. Batto, In the Beginning: Essays on Creation Motifs in the Ancient Near East and the Bible (2013) 65-75; Broekema, Inanna (2013) 81-84; Y.S. Chen, The Primeval Flood Catastrophe [...] (2013) 108-112; F. Hazelton, Three Kings of Warka: Enmerkar, Lugalbanda, Gilgamesh. Myths from Mesopotamia (2013) 10-32 (renarration); J. Cale Johnson, CHANE 68 (2014) 47-49, 59-61; P. Espak, The God Enki in Sumerian Royal Ideology and Mythology (2015) 194-198; D. Katz, CRRAI 60 (2017) 201-210 passim; M. Ceccarelli, Fabula 60 (2019) 105 sq., 113 sq.; C. Mittermayer, UAVA 15 (2019) 11.

Fluch über Akkade (3.1.i): J.-M. Durand, AEPHE 1974/1975, 154-181; Jacobsen, The Harps that once ... 359-374; ETCSL 2.1.5 (1998-1999); Black et alii, LAS 116-125; Attinger, TTS (2009, actualisé en 2015); J.L. Dahl/R.K. Englund, CDLI (2014-2015); A. Cavigneaux, dans K. Volk (ed.), Erzählungen aus dem Land Sumer (2015) 319-335 et 436; B.R. Foster, The Age of Agade: Inventing Empire in Ancient Mesopotamia (2016) 350-358, index p. 430. — Cf. J.-J. Glassner, BBVO 5 (1986) passim, surtout 66-77; D.O. Edzard, Mél. Sjöberg 99-105; F. Pomponio, Formule di maledizione [...] (1990) 83-87; G. Pettinato, I Sumeri (1991) 267-275 et 370 sq.; J.S. Cooper, HANES 5 (1993) 16 sq.; Rollinger, Frühformen 8-29 et passim; M. Liverani, HANES 5 56-59; Wilcke, Politik und Literatur 33-35; P. Steinkeller, JNES 52 (1993) 142; P. Mander, Mél. Moscati (1996) I 261-264; J. Cooper, CRRAI 45/I (2001) 132 sq. et 138-142; J.S. Cooper, JCS 38 (2006) 39-42; 45; F. Lara Peinado, Himnos sumerios (2006) 171-175; P. Attinger, NABU 2007/46; J.G. Westenholz, Mél. Sigrist (2008) 251-253; ead., dans: D. Konstan and K.A. Raaflaub (ed.), Epic and History (2010) 33; P. Michalowski, dans: A. Feldherr and G. Hardy (ed.), The Oxford History of Historical Writing I: Beginnings to AD 600 (2011) 16 sq.; Y.S. Chen, The Primeval Flood Catastrophe [...] (2013) 94-96; J.C. Johnson, CHANE 68 (2014) 47 sq. avec n. 13, 51-59; C. Wilcke, CRRAI (2015) 38-41; M.R. Bachvarova, dans: M.R. Bachvarova et al. (ed.), The Fall of Cities in the Mediterranean: Commemoration in Literature, Folk-Song, and Liturgy (2016) 43-46; S. Fink, AOAT 390/4 (2016) 124 sq.; P. Steinkeller, SANER 15 (2017) 79 sq.; E.S. Gerstenberger, Theologie des Lobens in sumerischen Hymnen (= ORA 28, 2018) 101-106.

Flut (3.1.j): Th. Jacobsen, JBL 100/4 (1981) 513-529; S.N. Kramer, AnSt. 33 (1983) 115-121; Jacobsen, The Harps that once ... 145-150; Bottéro/Kramer, Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme 564-567; W.H.Ph. Römer, TUAT III/3 (1993) 448-458; Jacobsen, The Context of Scripture I 513-515; ETCSL 1.7.4 (1998); H. Vanstiphout, Helden en goden van

Sumer (1998) 204-209; G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 146-151; Black et alii, *LAS* 212-215; J. Peterson, *JCS* 70 (2018) 37-51 (version d'Ur). — Cf. M.-J. Seux, dans Seux et al., *La création et le déluge d'après les textes du Proche-Orient ancien* (Supplément au Cahier *Evangile* 64 [1988]) 65-68; G. Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 71; A. Cavigneaux, *SMEA* 31 (1993) 97-101; J.R. Davila, *JNES* 54 (1995) 202 sq.; M. Dietrich, *MARG* 20 (2010) 46 sq.; H.S. Kvanvig, *Primeval History: Babylonian, Biblical and Enochic [...]* (2011) 84-89; Y.S. Chen, *JANER* 12 (2012) 179-183; Y.S. Chen, *The Primeval Flood Catastrophe [...]* (2013) 118-121; Lisman, *At the beginning* (2013) 53-55 et 291-295 = *AOAT* 409 (2013) 55-57 et 318-323; I. Finkel, *The Ark Before Noah: Decoding the Story of the Flood* (2014) 90-92.

Gilgameš und Akka (3.1.k): Jacobsen, *The Harps that once ...* 345-355; G. Pettinato, *La saga di Gilgamesh* (1992) 307-311 et 399-401; W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT* III/3 (1993) 549-559; D. Katz, *Gilgamesh and Akka* (= *Library of Oriental Texts* 1, Groningen, 1993) (édition); R.J. Tournay/A. Shaffer, *LAPO* 15 (1994) 282-291; Katz, *The Context of Scripture* I 550-552; H. Vanstiphout, *Helden en goden van Sumer* (1998) 47-54; A. George, *The Epic of Gilgamesh* (1999) 143-148, second revised and enlarged edition (2020) 99-105; *ETCSL* 1.8.1.1 (2000); D. Frayne, in: B.R. Foster (ed.), *The Epic of Gilgamesh* (2001) 99-104, (2019) 104-109; H. Neumann, *Gilgamesch und Akka*, dans: S. Franke (ed.), *Als die Götter Mensch waren* (2013) 91-95 et 120 sq.; H. Waetzoldt, dans K. Volk (ed.), *Erzählungen aus dem Land Sumer* (2015) 273-281 et 434 sq. — Cf. W.G. Lambert, *Or.* 49 (1980) 339 sq.; P. Michalowski, *BSOAS* 45 (1982) 577-578; J. Klein, *JAOS* 103 (1983) 201-204; Vanstiphout, *OLP* 17 (1986) 33-50; id., *AulOr.* 5 (1987) 129-141; id., *NABU* 1989/99; Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 162-166; id., *Rendiconti Morali, Accademia dei Lincei serie 9, vol. 5/1* (1994) 47-85; J.D. Evers, *AOAT* 241 (1995) 17-22; T. Marík, *ArOr.* 66 (1998) 265-269; G.J. Selz, *AOAT* 253 (1998) 313-319; C. Wilcke, *AOAT* 253, 457-485; Wu Yuhong, *NABU* 1998/103; Kramer/Molina, *El Matrimonio Sagrado* 45-48; P. Michalowski, *Suppl. au Dict. de la Bible* 72 (1999) 254; Vanstiphout, *JAOS* 119 (1999) 293-296; M. Civil, *AulOr.* 17-18 (1999-2000) 179-189; R.T. Ridley, *Or.* 69 (2000) 341-367; J.-D. Forest, *L'Epopée de Gilgamesh et sa postérité [...]* (2002) 218-223; A.R. George, *The Babylonian Gilgamesh Epic* (2003) 8 sq.; M. Lang, *AOAT* 325 (2005) 497-508; J. Sanmartín, *Epopéya de Gilgameš, rey de Uruk* (2005) 312-314; 328; G. Pettinato, *Dal mare alla montagna dei cedri. Il poema sumerico di Enmerkar ed Ensuĝgiranna* (2006) 60-62; S. Anthonioz, *Semitica et Classica* 2 (2009) 17-19; J. Keetman, *Babel und Bibel* 6 (2012) 15-30; J.C. Johnson, *AVO* 15 (2015) 169-172; S. Franke, dans: M. Grohmann (ed.), *Identität und Schrift. Fortschreibungsprozesse als Mittel religiöser Identitätsbildung* (2017) 20-22; L.M. Pryke, *Ishtar: Gods and Heroes of the Ancient World* (2017) 158 sq.; E.S. Gerstenberger, *Theologie des Lobens in sumerischen Hymnen* (= *ORA* 28, 2018) 131-136; C. Mittermayer, *UAVA* 15 (2019) 32 sq.

Gilgameš, Enkidu und die Unterwelt (1.3.l): S.N. Kramer, *The Sumerians* 197-205; G. Pettinato, *La saga di Gilgamesh* (1992) 329-342 et 409-412; R.J. Tournay/A. Shaffer, *LAPO* 15 (1994) 248-274; *ETCSL* 1.8.1.4 (1998-2000); A. George, *The Epic of Gilgamesh* (1999) 175-195, second revised and enlarged edition (2020) 131-145; D. Frayne, in: B.R. Foster (ed.), *The Epic of Gilgamesh* (2001) 129-143, (2019) 109-125; G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 439-457; Black et alii, *LAS* 31-40; A. Gadotti, "Gilgameš, Enkidu and the Netherworld" and the Sumerian Gilgameš Cycle, Ph. D. diss., The John Hopkins University 2005 (édition); Attinger, *TTS* (2008-2009, actualisé en 2015); Attinger, *TUAT* NF 8 (2015) 24-37; Attinger, dans K. Volk (ed.), *Erzählungen aus dem Land Sumer* (2015) 297-316 et 435 sq. — Cf. B. Alster, *RA* 68 (1974) 55-60 et *ASJ* 5 (1983) 1-16; A. Koefoed, *ASJ* 5 (1983) 17-

23; W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT II/1* (1986) 36-45; J. Tropper, *WO 17* (1986) 19-24; J. Bauer, *OPSNKF 11* (1989) 21 sqq.; Kramer/Maier, *Myths of Enki* 82 sq.; J. Tropper, *AOAT 223* (1989) 62-69; T. Kuwabara, *The Netherworld in Sumerian-Akkadian Literature* (Ph. D., Univ. of California at Berkeley, 1991) 19-37; Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 173-177, 312 et 330 sq.; Th. Jacobsen, *Mél. Hallo* 120-123; D.O. Edzard, *BCSMS 27* (1994) 12 sq.; K. Hecker, *TUAT III/4* (1994) 739-744; E. Frahm, *JCS 51* (1999) 76-78; V.K. Afanasieva, *VDI 233* (2000) 53-63; A. Cavigneaux/F. Al-Rawi, *Iraq 62* (2000) 1-19; Pettinato, *Studi Cagni* (2000) 875-878; J.-D. Forest, *L'Épopée de Gilgamesh et sa postérité [...] (2002) 196-211*; J. Klein, dans: T. Abusch (ed.), *Riches Hidden in Secret Places: Ancient Near Eastern Studies in Memory of Thorkild Jacobsen* (2002) 187-201; M. Streck, *Or. 71* (2002) 194-196; A.R. George, *The Babylonian Gilgamesh Epic* (2003) 12-14, 45-54, 743-777 et 898-905 (édition des ll. 172-fin); D. Katz, *The Image of the Netherworld in the Sumerian Sources* (2003) passim (index des lignes discutées p. 481); Pettinato, *I miti degli inferi assiro-babilonesi* (2003) 137 sq., 158-160 et 162-167; D.O. Edzard, *OBO 160/4* (2004) 494 et n. 34, 558 n. 267, 605-609; B. Alster, *Wisdom of Ancient Sumer* (2005) 339-341; F. Joannès, *Ktema 30* (2005) 81-83; J. Sanmartín, *Epopeya de Gilgameš, rey de Uruk* (2005) 322-326; 329 sq.; A.J. Ferrara, *CM 35* (2006) 47-66; R. Rollinger, *Nikephoros 19* (2006) 9-44 passim, surtout 15-24 et 33-38; J. Keetman, *BiOr. 64* (2007) 5-31.; Peterson, *Faunal Conception 442-449* (ll. 14-26 //); V. Van der Stede, *Lettres orientales 12* (2007) 118-121; Wilcke, *Anfänge* (2007) 26 sq.; R. Rollinger, *JCS 60* (2008) 15-23; J.A. Lynch, *Gilgamesh's Ghosts: The Dead, Textual Variation, and the Mesopotamian Scribal Tradition*. Ph. D., Univ. of California 2010; Maul, S.M., *Himmelfahrt und Abstieg in die Unterwelt — altorientalische Mythe von Jenseitsreisen*, dans: E. Hornung und A. Schweizer (ed.), *Jenseitsreisen, Eranos 2009 und 2010* (2011) 246-270 (version akkadienne de GEN: 265-270); Broekema, *Inanna* (2013) 87-90; Lisman, *At the beginning* (2013) 42-46 et 258-267 = *AOAT 409* (2013) 44-48 et 282-292; A.-C. Rendu Loisel, *Heurs et malheurs du jardinier dans la littérature sumérienne*, dans: D. Barbu et al. (ed.), *Mondes clos, cultures et jardins* (2013) 80-82 et 340 sq.; A. Annus and M. Sarv, *Melammu Symposia 7* (2015) 285-296, surtout 289-294; A. Jordanova, *Untersuchungen zur Gestalt einer Unterweltsgöttin: Ereškigal nach den sumerischen und akkadischen Quellentexten*. Dissertation zur Erlangung des akademischen Grades Doctor Philosophiae (Dr. phil.), Universität Leipzig (2015) 361-369; N.A. Corfù, *AOAT 439* (2016) 37-46; S.J. Milstein, *Tracking the Master Scribe: Revision through Introduction in Biblical and Mesopotamian Literature* (2016) 136-144; J.A. Lynch, *OBO SA 40* (2018) 241-244; P. Steinkeller, *JANEH 5* (2018) 156-172 passim; A. Gadotti/A. Kleinerman, *Mél. Sasson* (2020) 138-143 (nouveau duplicat); T. Simkó, *JCS 72* (2020) 28-30.

Gilgameš und der Himmelsstier (3.1.m): G. Pettinato, *La saga di Gilgamesh* (1992) 324-328 et 408; A. Cavigneaux/F.N.H. Al-Rawi, *RA 87* (1993) 97-129 (édition); *ETCSL 1.8.1.2* (1998); A. George, *The Epic of Gilgamesh* (1999) 166-175, second revised and enlarged edition (2020) 122-131; D. Frayne, in: B.R. Foster (ed.), *The Epic of Gilgamesh* (2001) 120-127, (2019) 138-146; . Klein/Y. Sefati, *From the Workshop of the Mesopotamian Scribe: Literary and Scholarly Texts from the Old Babylonian Period* (2019) 5-74 (édition partielle). — Cf. C. Wilcke, *Voix de l'opposition* 57-59; Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 177-179; Wilcke, *Politik und Literatur* 57 sq.; A.R. George, *CRRAI 47* (2002) 144-149; J.-D. Forest, *L'Épopée de Gilgamesh et sa postérité [...] (2002) 215-218*; M. Streck, *Or. 71* (2002) 222 sq.; A.R. George, *The Babylonian Gilgamesh Epic* (2003) 11 sq.; B. Alster, *PIHANS 100* (2004) 34 sq.; Cf. A. Gadotti, *CM 35* (2006) 67-83 passim.; S. Anthonioz, *Semitica et Classica 2* (2009) 21 sq.; S. Ponchia, *StOr. 106* (2009) 399-407; A.R. George, *Mém. Black* 101-115; J.L.

Cooley, *Poetic Astronomy in the Ancient Near East [...]* (2013) 173-178; S. Franke, dans: M. Grohmann (ed.), *Identität und Schrift. Fortschreibungsprozesse als Mittel religiöser Identitätsbildung* (2017) 24-29 (versions sum. et akk.); P. Steinkeller, *JANEH* 5 (2018) 158 sq.; J. Klein/Y. Sefati, *Mél. Sasson* (2020) 175-185.

Gilgameš und Ħuwawa (3.1.n) 1. **version A**: D.O. Edzard, *ZA* 80 (1990) 165-203 et *ZA* 81 (1991) 165-233 (édition); G. Pettinato, *La saga di Gilgamesh* (1992) 312-323 et 401-408; Edzard, *TUAT* III/3 (1993) 540-549; id., *Bayerische Akademie der Wissenschaften, Philosophisch-historische Klasse, Sitzungsberichte Jahrgang 1993, Heft 4* (München, 1993) 35-45; R.J. Tournay/A. Shaffer, *LPO* 15 (1994) 292-305; H. Vanstiphout, *Helden en goden van Sumer* (1998) 55-67; A. George, *The Epic of Gilgamesh* (1999) 149-161, second revised and enlarged edition (2020) 105-116; *ETCSL* 1.8.1.5 (1999-2000); D. Frayne, in: B.R. Foster (ed.), *The Epic of Gilgamesh* (2001) 104-115, (2019) 125-138; Black et alii, *LAS* 343-352; W.H.Ph. Römer, *UF* 37 (2005) 517-555; Delnero, *Variation* 2396-2474 (partition); D.E. Fleming/S.J. Milstein, *CM* 39 (2010) passim, surtout 182-195; E. Smith, *The Sumerian Mythographic Tradition and Its Implications for Genesis 1-11*, PhD diss., University of Bristol and Trinity College 2012, 108-129 (translittération, traduction et très bref commentaire); Edzard, dans K. Volk (ed.), *Erzählungen aus dem Land Sumer* (2015) 283-295 et 435. — Cf. J. Hansman, *Iraq* 38 (1976) 23-35; N. Forsyth, *ASJ* 3 (1981) 13-29; M. deJong Ellis, *AfO* 28 (1981-1982) 123-131; A. Shaffer, *JAOS* 103 (1983) 307-313; W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT* II/5 (1989) 713-715; G. Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 166-173; B. Alster, *BSOAS* 55 (1992) 1-8; id., *Mesopotamian Epic Literature* 65-69; Edzard, *BCSMS* 27 (1994) 9 sq.; D. Katz, *NABU* 1995/29; G. Steiner, *ASJ* 18 (1996) 187-215; Kramer/Molina, *El Matrimonio Sagrado* 48-53; A. Cavigneaux/F. Al-Rawi, *Iraq* 62 (2000) 5 sq.; J. Klein/K. Abraham, *HANE/M-III/3* (2000) 63-73; J.-D. Forest, *L'Épopée de Gilgamesh et sa postérité [...]* (2002) 211-215; M. Streck, *Or.* 71 (2002) 227 sq.; M. Civil, *Mél. Wilcke* (2003) 77-86; A.R. George, *The Babylonian Gilgamesh Epic* (2003) 9 sq. 2; J. Sanmartín, *Epopeya de Gilgameš, rey de Uruk* (2005) 314-319; 328 sq.; G. Pettinato, *Dal mare alla montagna dei cedri. Il poema sumerico di Enmerkar ed Ensuĥgiranna* (2006) 62-64; S. Anthonioz, *Semitica et Classica* 2 (2009) 19-21; P. Michalowski, dans: K.A. Raaflaub and R.J.A. Talbert (ed.), *Geography and Ethnography* (2010) 160 sq./165 n. 13 sq.; C. Mittermayer, *OBO* 245 (2010) 135-164 passim; J. Taylor, *Mém. Black* 351-360; L. Verderame, *AOAT* 441 (2017) 285-287 et 294-296. **version B**: Edzard, *Bayerische Akademie der Wissenschaften, Philosophisch-historische Klasse, Sitzungsberichte Jahrgang 1993, Heft 4* 1-61 (édition); A. George, *The Epic of Gilgamesh* (1999) 162-166, second revised and enlarged edition (2020) 105 sq. et 117-122; *ETCSL* 1.8.1.5.1 (1999-2000); D. Frayne, in: B.R. Foster (ed.), *The Epic of Gilgamesh* (2001) 115-120; D.E. Fleming/S.J. Milstein, *CM* 39 (2010) passim, surtout 196-205. — Cf. A. Ganter, *NABU* 1995/41; G. Steiner, *ASJ* 18 (1996) 187-215; id., *CRRAI* 43 (1998) 373-376; G. Marchesi, *Studi Cagni* (2000) 673-684; M. Streck, *Or.* 71 (2002) 220 sq.; A.R. George, *The Babylonian Gilgamesh Epic* (2003) 10 sq.; C. Mittermayer, *OBO* 245 (2010) 135-164 passim; J.L. Cooley, *Poetic Astronomy in the Ancient Near East [...]* (2013) 89-93; N. Samet, *Biblica* 96 (2015) 379-382; L. Feldt, *Numen* 63 (2016) 357-360, 369-373; E.S. Gerstenberger, *Theologie des Lobens in sumerischen Hymnen (= ORA 28, 2018)* 118 sq.

Gilgameš in der Unterwelt (3.1.o): G. Pettinato, *La saga di Gilgamesh* (1992) 343-347 et 412 sq.; *ETCSL* 1.8.1.3 (1998-2000); A. George, *The Epic of Gilgamesh* (1999) 195-208, second revised and enlarged edition (2020) 122-131; A. Cavigneaux/F.N.H. Al-Rawi, *Gilgameš et la Mort (= Textes de Tell Haddad VI)*, *CM* 19 (2000); D. Frayne, in: B.R. Foster

(ed.), *The Epic of Gilgamesh* (2001) 143-154, (2019) 148-158, (2019)109-125; G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 458-476; N. Veldhuis, *JCS* 53 (2001) 133-148. — Cf. R. Jestin, *Syria* 33 (1956) 113-118; J. van Dijk, *HSAO* 1 (1967) 248-251; Th. Jacobsen, *Mesop.* 8 (1980) 19-24; W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT II/1* (1986) 34-36; T. Kuwabara, *The Netherworld in Sumerian-Akkadian Literature* (Ph. D., Univ. of California at Berkeley, 1991) 71-76; Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 181-183; A. Cavigneaux/F. al-Rawi, *Iraq* 55 (1993) 93; R. Rollinger, *Nikephoros* 7 (1994) 37 sq.; J.-D. Forest, *L'Épopée de Gilgamesh et sa postérité [...]* (2002) 221-226; M. Streck, *Or.* 71 (2002) 221 sq.; A.R. George, *The Babylonian Gilgamesh Epic* (2003) 14-17; D. Katz, *The Image of the Netherworld in the Sumerian Sources* (2003) passim (index des lignes discutées p. 480); G. Marchesi, *Or.* 73 (2004) 156-161; C. Wilcke, *NABU* 2004/98; J. Sanmartín, *Epopeya de Gilgameš, rey de Uruk* (2005) 326 sq.; 330; A. Zgoll, *AOAT* 333 (2006) 101-104; J. Keetman, *JNES* 67 (2008) 164 sq.; S. Anthonioz, *OBO* 257 (2012) 82-92; W. Sallaberger, *Der Tod des göttlichen Königs [...]*, in: M. Fieger und M. Weder (ed.), *Krankheit und Sterben. Ein interprofessioneller Dialog (= Das Alte Testament im Dialog* 6, 2012) 245-271 (Gilgameš in der Unterwelt: 257-265); Y.S. Chen, *The Primeval Flood Catastrophe [...]* (2013) 106-108; N. Artemov, *CRRAI* 55 (2014) 38-41; Jordanova, A., *Untersuchungen zur Gestalt einer Unterweltsgöttin: Ereškigal nach den sumerischen und akkadischen Quellentexten. Dissertation zur Erlangung des akademischen Grades Doctor Philosophiae (Dr. phil.), Universität Leipzig* (2015) 357-361; L.M. Pryke, *Ishtar: Gods and Heroes of the Ancient World* (2017) 153-159; Sallaberger, W., *Tuna el-Gebel* 9 (2019) 99-102.

Götterreisen (3.1.p): Cf. en général R. Mayer-Opificius, *Mitteilungen für Anthropologie und Religionsgeschichte* 15 (2000; paru en 2003) 81-102; G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 305 sq.; K. Wagensooner, *WZKM* 97 (2001) 541-559; id., *Götterreisen* (2005).

Enkis Reise nach Nippur (3.1.p 1) (=!) **Eridu-Hymne** (3.2.3.b): Castellino, *TSA* 209-214; Bottéro/Kramer, *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme* 142-150; Kramer/Maier, *Myths of Enki* 69-74; *ETCSL* 1.1.4 (1999); G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 358-364; Black et alii, *LAS* 330-333; Delnero, *Variation 2239-2290* (partition); F. Lara Peinado, *Himnos sumerios* (2006) 225-231; M. Ceccarelli, *OBO* 256 (2012) 89-118 (édition; v. id., *NABU* 2013/40); J. Bauer, dans K. Volk (ed.), *Erzählungen aus dem Land Sumer* (2015) 365-372 et 437. — Cf. G. Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 332 sq.; J. Bottéro, *La plus vieille Religion. En Mésopotamie* (1998) 278-282 (traduction partielle); R.A. Casey, *Inanna and Enki in Sumer: an Ancient Conflict Revisited* (Ph. D., The California Institute of Integral Studies 1998) 81-99; M. Streck, *Or.* 71 (2002) 198; Wagensooner, *Götterreisen* (2005) 81-91; Y.S. Chen, *The Primeval Flood Catastrophe [...]* (2013) 85; P. Espak, *The God Enki in Sumerian Royal Ideology and Mythology* (2015) 99 sq.; A.-C. Rendu Loisel, *Mythos* 11 (2017) 40 sq.; P. Espak, *Studia Orientalia Tartuensia* 2019 42-44.

Nannas Reise nach Nippur (3.1.p 2): W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT II/2* (1987) 175-189; Bottéro/Kramer, *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme* 128-142; *ETCSL* 1.5.1 (1998); G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 337-351; Black et alii, *LAS* 147-154. — Cf. C. Wilcke, *AfO* 24 (1973) 2-6; A.J. Ferrara, *RA* 68 (1974) 169-172; G. Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 364 sq.; M. Streck, *Or.* 71 (2002) 227 sq.; Wagensooner, *Götterreisen* (2005) 35-55.

Gudam (3.1.q): W.H.Ph. Römer, *BiOr.* 48 (1991) 363-378 (édition); *ETCSL* 1.3.4 (1998-2000); D. Frayne, in: B.R. Foster (ed.), *The Epic of Gilgamesh* (2001) 127-129; B.

Alster, *PIHANS* 100 (2004) 21-45 (édition). — Cf. A. Gadotti, *GEN* (2005) 166-170; ead., *CM* 35 (2006) 67-83.

Inanna und Bilulu (3.1.r): Bottéro/Kramer, *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme* 330-337; *ETCSL* 1.4.4 (1998); G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 396-403. — Cf. T. Kuwabara, *The Netherworld in Sumero-Akkadian Literature* (Ph. D., Univ. of California at Berkeley, 1991) 59-63; Kramer/Molina, *El Matrimonio Sagrado* 159; K. Sonik, *JAOS* 132 (2012) 389 sq.; Gadotti, *The feminine in myths and epic* (2014) 47-51, 55 sq.; Broekema, *Inanna* (2013) 315 sq.; M. Ceccarelli, *Fabula* 60 (2019) 117 sq. (à propos des ll. 98-110).

Inanna und Ebih (3.1.s): Bottéro/Kramer, *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme* 219-229; P. Attinger, *ZA* 88 (1998) 164-195 (édition); *ETCSL* 1.3.2 (1998-1999); Betty De Shong Meador, *Inanna, Lady of Largest Heart* (2000) 89-113 et 201-203; G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 284-294; Black et alii, *LAS* 334-338; Delnero, *Variation* 2291-2359 (partition); Attinger, *TTS* (2011, actualisé en 2015); Attinger, *TUAT NF* 8 (2015) 37-45; Attinger, dans K. Volk (ed.), *Erzählungen aus dem Land Sumer* (2015) 353-363 et 437; B.R. Foster, *The Age of Agade: Inventing Empire in Ancient Mesopotamia* (2016) 341-347, index p. 432; C. Halton/S. Svärd, *Women's Writing of Ancient Mesopotamia: An Anthology of the Earliest Female Authors* (2018) 87-93. — Cf. Wilcke, *Politik und Literatur* 47-49; R.A. Casey, *Inanna and Enki in Sumer: an Ancient Conflict Revisited* (Ph. D., The California Institute of Integral Studies 1998) 232-257; A. Zgoll, *HANE/M III/2* (2000) 83-86 et 89 sq.; J. Cooper, *CRRAI* 45/I (2001) 135 n. 20 et 143 avec n. 58; M. Streck, *Or.* 71 (2002) 223-225; F. Karahashi, *JNES* 63 (2004) 111-118; M. Jaques, *ZA* 94 (2004) 202-225; P. Delnero, *Mél. Eichler* (2011) 123-149; Broekema, *Inanna* (2013) 200-206; L. Feldt, *Numen* 63 (2016) 357-360, 364-366; I. Peled, *AOAT* 435 (2016) 66-68; Ll. Feliu, dans: J.J. Justel and A. Garcia-Ventura (ed.), *Las mujeres en el Oriente cuneiforme* (2018) 133 sq.; A. Perdibon, *LAOS* 11 (2019) 63-66; ead., *Distant Worlds Journal* 4 (2020) 127-131.

Inanna und Enki (3.1.t): Bottéro/Kramer, *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme* 230-256; *ETCSL* 1.3.1 (1998); G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 307-356. — Cf. B. Alster, *ZA* 64 (1975) 20-34; H. Waetzoldt, *BiOr.* 32 (1975) 382-384; H. Limet, *Mél. Sjöberg* 361 sq. et 364; J.-J. Glassner, *CRRAI* 35 (1988, ed. 1992) 55-86; G. Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 362-364; Wilcke, *Politik und Literatur* 44 sq.; Penglase, *Greek Myths* 41-44; G. Farber, *JNES* 54 (1995) 287-292; id., *The Context of Scripture I* 522-526 (traduction partielle); R.A. Casey, *Inanna and Enki in Sumer: an Ancient Conflict Revisited* (Ph. D., The California Institute of Integral Studies 1998) 100-127; G.J. Selz, *Mél. Dux* (2003) 251-254; Wagensooner, *Götterreisen* (2005) 191-194; G. Pettinato, *Dal mare alla montagna dei cedri. Il poema sumerico di Enmerkar ed Ensuhgiranna* (2006) C.E. Barrett, *JANER* 7 (2007) 21 sq.; I. Slobodzianek, *Acquérir, exprimer et transmettre les "pouvoirs" divins: une comparaison entre Aphrodite et Inanna/Ištar*, thèse de doctorat, Toulouse 2012 (<https://de.scribd.com/document/135631970/Acquerir-exprimer-et-transmettre-les-pouvoirs-divins-Une-comparaison-entre-Aphrodite-et-Inanna-Istar>) 29-45, 272-275; Broekema, *Inanna* (2013) 281-288; Y.S. Chen, *The Primeval Flood Catastrophe [...]* (2013) 79 sq.; G.J. Selz, *Mél. de Meis* (2014) 64 sq.; C. Bonnet/I. Slobodzianek, *De la steppe au bateau céleste ou comment Inanna accomplit son destin entre mythe et rite*, dans: N. Belayche/V. Pirenne-Delforge, *Fabriquer du divin. Constructions et ajustements de la représentation des dieux dans l'Antiquité* (2015) 21-40 passim; P. Espak, *The God Enki in Sumerian Royal Ideology and Mythology* (2015) 100-102; I. Peled, *AOAT* 435 (2016) 68-71; L.M. Pryke, *Ishtar: Gods and*

Heroes of the Ancient World (2017) 91-94; G.B. Selz, *Melammu* 9 (2018) 431-433; P. Espak, *Studia Orientalia Tartuensia* 2019 44-46.

Inannas Gang zur Unterwelt (3.1.u): D. Wolkstein/S.N. Kramer, *Inanna, Queen of Heaven and Earth* [...] (1983) 51-85 et 206; Jacobsen, *The Harps that once ...* 205-232; Bottéro/Kramer, *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme* 276-295; D.D. Jones, *She spoke to them with a stormy heart: The politics of reading ancient (or other) narrative* (Ph. D., Univ. of Minnesota 1993) passim, surtout 1 sqq., 102-139, 189-229 (traduction), 230-266, 271-275; W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT* III/3 (1993) 458-495; ETCSL 1.4.1 (1998); H. Vanstiphout, *Helden en goden van Sumer* (1998) 210-228; G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 260-283; Black et alii, *LAS* 65-76; H. Waetzoldt, dans K. Volk (ed.), *Erzählungen aus dem Land Sumer* (2015) 375-398 et 437-441. — Cf. Kramer, *The Sacred Marriage Rite: Aspects of Faith, Myth, and Ritual in Ancient Sumer* (1969) 108-119 et 154-156 (trad. en français par J. Bottéro dans S.N. Kramer, *Le mariage sacré à Sumer et Babylone* [1983] 136-146 et 168-170, traduction en espagnol par M. Molina dans S.N. Kramer, *El Matrimonio Sagrado en la Antigua Sumer. Traducción y adaptación de Manuel Molina* [= Colección: Estudios Orientales 11, 1999] 128-138 et 141); A. Draffkorn Kilmer, *UF* 3 (1971) 299-308; D. Irvin, *AOAT* 32 (1978) 38 sq.; V. Afanasieva, *ZA* 70 (1980) 161-169; S.N. Kramer, *PAPS* 124 (1980) 299-312; id., *BCSMS* 4 (1982) 26-32; G. Buccellati, *SMS* 4/3 (1982) 3-7; W. Burkert, *OBO* 48 (1982) 66-68; W. Heimpel, *SMS* 4/3 9-13; A.R. George, *JCS* 37 (1985) 109-113; T. Kuwabara, *The Netherworld in Sumer-Akkadian Literature* (Ph. D., Univ. of California at Berkeley, 1991) 7-18; G. Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 327-330; R.D. Wexler, *The Concepts of Mortality and Immortality in Ancient Mesopotamia* (Ph. D., Univ. of California 1993) 157-182; Wilcke, *Politik und Literatur* 49-55; Penglase, *Greek Myths* 17-26 et 246 sq.; J.D. Evers, *AOAT* 241 (1995) 65-98; D. Katz, *ZA* 85 (1995) 221-233; B. Alster, *ASJ* 18 (1996) 1-18; Katz, *ASJ* 18 (1996) 93-102; W. Heimpel, *RIA* 8/7-8 (1997) 556 sq.; R.A. Casey, *Inanna and Enki in Sumer: an Ancient Conflict Revisited* (Ph. D., The California Institute of Integral Studies 1998) 258-291; Kramer/Molina, *El Matrimonio Sagrado* 128-138 et 141; J. Cooper, *CRRAI* 45/I (2001) 143 sq.; T.N.D. Mettinger, *The Riddle of Resurrection* [...] (= *Coniectanea Biblica Old Testament Series* 50, 2001), 187-190; P. Lapinkivi, *CRRAI* 47 (2002) 327-335 passim; M. Streck, *Or.* 71 (2002) 227-229; M.M. Fritz, *AOAT* 307 (2003) 102-104; D. Katz, *The Image of the Netherworld in the Sumerian Sources* (2003) passim, surtout 251-287 (index des lignes discutées p. 482); Pettinato, *I miti degli inferi assiro-babilonesi* (2003) 135-137; D.O. Edzard, *OBO* 160/4 (2004) 495-497, 600 sq.; B. Groneberg, *Die Götter des Zweistromlandes* 181-184; Lapinkivi, *SAAS* 15 (2004) 189-194; Wagensohn, *Götterreisen* (2005) 195-198; A.J. Ferrara, *CM* 31 (2006) 127-138; C.E. Barrett, *JANER* 7 (2007) 20 sqq. passim.; V. Van der Stede, *Lettres orientales* 12 (2007) 129-147 passim; A.J. Ferrara, *Mél. Abusch* (2010) 27-47 passim; P. Lapinkivi, *SAACT* 6 (2010) 35-93 passim (comparaison avec *La descente d'Ištar*); J.A. Lynch, *Gilgamesh's Ghosts: The Dead, Textual Variation, and Mesopotamian Scribal Tradition* (Ph. D., Univ. of California 2010) 191-201; I. Slobodzianek, *Mythos* 4 n.s. (2010) 32-35; B. Alster, *OLA* 189 (2011) 55-79; C. Bonnet/I. Slobodzianek, dans: F. Gherchanoc et V. Huet (ed.), *Vêtements antiques. S'habiller, se déshabiller dans les mondes anciens* (2012) 135-148; V. Grandpierre, *Sexe et amour de Sumer à Babylone* (2012) 52-54; I. Slobodzianek, *Acquérir, exprimer et transmettre les "pouvoirs" divins: une comparaison entre Aphrodite et Inanna/Ištar*, thèse de doctorat, Toulouse 2012 (<https://de.scribd.com/document/135631970/Acquerir-exprimer-et-transmettre-les-pouvoirs-divins-Une-comparaison-entre-Aphrodite-et-Inanna-Istar>) 147-155, 185-208, 265-271; K. Sonik, *JAOS* 132 (2012) 387-389; Broekema, *Inanna* (2013) 455-469; T.W.P.H. Tanaka, *Dress and Identity in Old Babylonian Texts* (Ph. D. diss., University of

California, Berkeley, 2013) 20-65; A. Jordanova, Untersuchungen zur Gestalt einer Unterweltsgöttin: Ereškigal nach den sumerischen und akkadischen Quellentexten. Dissertation zur Erlangung des akademischen Grades Doctor Philosophiae (Dr. phil.), Universität Leipzig (2015) 346-251; D. Katz, CRRAI 57 (2015) 64-71; I. Peled, AOAT 435 (2016) 50-55, 60-63; L.M. Pryke, *Ishtar: Gods and Heroes of the Ancient World* (2017) 101-110; G.J. Selz, AOAT 434 (2017) 277-290; R. Cabrera, JNSL 44 (2018) 41-79 passim; Ll. Feliu, dans: J.J. Justel and A. Garcia-Ventura (ed.), *Las mujeres en el Oriente cuneiforme* (2018) 130-132; B. Dedović, "Inanna's Descent to the Netherworld": A centennial survey of scholarship, artifacts, and translations, Bachelor of Arts diploma in History, University of Maryland, 2019; V. Muller, *Mél. Rouault* (2019) 212 sq.; C. Zgoll, *Tractatus mythologicus* [...] (= *Mythological Studies* 1 [2019]) 540 sq.; A. Zgoll, *Durch Tod zur Macht, selbst über den Tod.* [...], dans: A. Zgoll/C. Zgoll (ed.), *Mythische Sphärenwechsel. Methodisch neue Zugänge zu antiken Mythen in Orient und Okzident* (= *Mythological Studies* 2 [2020]) 83-159 passim; A. Zgoll/C. Zgoll, *CM* 50 (2020) 752-802 passim.

Inanna und Šukalle-tuda (3.1.v): Bottéro/Kramer, *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme* 257-271; K. Volk, *Inanna und Šukaletuda* [...] (= *SANTAG* 3, 1995) (édition); *ETCSL* 1.3.3 (1999-2000); G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 380-395; Black et alii, *LAS* 197-205; Attinger, *TTS* (2011, actualisé en 2015). — Cf. B. Alster, *ZA* 64 (1975) 30-34; Wilcke, *Politik und Literatur* 56 sq.; B. Hruška, *ArOr.* 66 (1998) 318-324; J. Cooper, *CRRAI* 45/I (2001) 142-144; G.J. Selz, *JAC* 16 (2001) 46-58; M.-F. Besnier, *CRRAI* 47 (2002) 60-64, 67, 69; M. Streck, *Or.* 71 (2002) 214-216; T. Marík, *WZKM* 93 (2003) 147-166; P. Lapinkivi, *SAAS* 15 (2004) 220-226; Volk, *RIA* 10/3-4 (2004) 288 sq.; J.L. Cooley, *JANER* 8 (2008) 75-98; id., *Kaskal* 5 (2008) 161-172; A. Gadotti, *JAOS* 129 (2009) 77 sq.; L. Vacin, *Šulgi of Ur: Life, Deeds, Ideology and Legacy of a Mesopotamian Ruler as Reflected primarily in Literary Texts* (PhD, University of London, 2011) 107-110; Broekema, *Inanna* (2013) 288-292; J.L. Cooley, *Poetic Astronomy in the Ancient Near East* [...] (2013) 160-173; C. Mittermayer, *ORA* 10 (2013) 35-38; A.-C. Rendu Loisel, *Heurs et malheurs du jardinier dans la littérature sumérienne*, dans: D. Barbu et al. (ed.), *Mondes clos, cultures et jardins* (2013) 73-78 et 339 sq.; S. Parpola, *Melammu* 2014, 19; I. Slobodzianek, dans C. Bonnet et al. (ed.), *Puissances divines à l'épreuve du comparatisme: constructions, variations et réseaux relationnels* (= *Bibliothèque de l'École des Hautes Études, sciences religieuses* vol. 175, 2016) 265-272; L.M. Pryke, *Ishtar: Gods and Heroes of the Ancient World* (2017) 71-83, 147 sq.; C. Zgoll, *Tractatus mythologicus* [...] (= *Mythological Studies* 1 [2019]) 541 sq.; A. Zgoll, *Durch Tod zur Macht, selbst über den Tod.* [...], dans: A. Zgoll/C. Zgoll (ed.), *Mythische Sphärenwechsel. Methodisch neue Zugänge zu antiken Mythen in Orient und Okzident* (= *Mythological Studies* 2 [2020]) 108-127.

Lugalbanda I (3.1.w): J. Black, *Reading Sumerian Poetry* (London 1998) 120-124 et 176-184; *ETCSL* 1.8.2.1 (1998); H. Vanstiphout, *Helden en goden van Sumer* (1998) 114-129; Black et alii, *LAS* 11-22; Vanstiphout, *Epics of Sumerian Kings: The Matter of Aratta* (= *Writings from the Ancient World* 20, 2004) 99-131 et 159-163; C. Wilcke, dans K. Volk (ed.), *Erzählungen aus dem Land Sumer* (2015) 206-220, 226-254, 422-427. — Cf. Hall, *Nanna/Suen* 529-533; W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT* II/1 (1986) 32-34; Wilcke, *RIA* 7, 1/2 (1987) 121-125 et 129 sq. s.v. *Lugalbanda* (bibl. p. 121); B. Alster, *Mél. Moran* 59-72 passim; G. Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 153-157; Alster, *Mesopotamian Epic Literature* 56-59; H.L.J. Vanstiphout, *OLP* 26 (1995) 5-20; id., *CRRAI* 43 (1998) 397-412; G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 119 sq.; Vanstiphout, dans: T. Abusch (ed.), *Riches Hidden in Secret Places:*

Ancient Near Eastern Studies in Memory of Thorkild Jacobsen (2002) 259-289 passim; M. Streck, *Or.* 71 (2002) 200-202; Alster, *Iraq* 67 (2005) 61-71; D. Katz, *CM* 35 (2006) 110-113.; G. Pettinato, *Dal mare alla montagna dei cedri. Il poema sumerico di Enmerkar ed Ensuhgiranna* (2006) 47-52; Wilcke, *Anfänge* (2007) 27 sq./49-51; F. Hazelton, *Three Kings of Warka: Enmerkar, Lugalbanda, Gilgamesh. Myths from Mesopotamia* (2013) 33-53 (renarration de Lugalb. I et II); J.Z. Wee, *JNES* 73 (2014) 23-42 passim; Wilcke, *CRRAI* 57 (2015) 37 sq., 41-44 et 48; L. Feldt, *Numen* 63 (2016) 357-360, 366-369; A. Perdibon, *LAOS* 11 (2019) 48 sq.

Lugalbanda II (3.1.x): Jacobsen, *The Harps that once ...* 320-344; W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT III/3* (1993) 507-539; J. Black, *Reading Sumerian Poetry* (London 1998) passim (traduction pp. 58-64); *ETCSL* 1.8.2.2 (1998); H. Vanstiphout, *Helden en goden van Sumer* (1998) 130-149; Black et alii, *LAS* 22-31; Vanstiphout, *Epics of Sumerian Kings: The Matter of Aratta (= Writings from the Ancient World 20, 2004)* 132-159 et 163-165; C. Wilcke, dans K. Volk (ed.), *Erzählungen aus dem Land Sumer* (2015) 206-208, 220-226, 254-272, 427-434. — Cf. H. Sauren, *JEOL* 22 (1971/1972) 288-295; R.S. Falkowitz, *JAOS* 103 (1983) 103-114; Wilcke, *RIA* 7, 1/2 (1987) 125-130; B. Alster, *Mél. Moran* 59-72 passim; G. Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 157-161; Alster, *Mesopotamian Epic Literature* 56-59; D.O. Edzard, *BCSMS* 27 (1994) 11; H.L.J. Vanstiphout, *OLP* 26 (1995) 5-20; ID, dans: T. Abusch (ed.), *Riches Hidden in Secret Places: Ancient Near Eastern Studies in Memory of Thorkild Jacobsen* (2002) 259-289 passim; J. Polonsky, *The Rise of the Sun God and the Determination of Destiny in Ancient Mesopotamia* (PhD., Univ. of Philadelphia 2002) 712-718; C. Schmidt, *BaM* 36 (2005) 55 sq.; G. Pettinato, *Dal mare alla montagna dei cedri. Il poema sumerico di Enmerkar ed Ensuhgiranna* (2006) 51-56; F. Hazelton, *Three Kings of Warka: Enmerkar, Lugalbanda, Gilgamesh. Myths from Mesopotamia* (2013) 33-53 (renarration de Lugalb. I et II); L. Feldt, *Numen* 63 (2016) 357-360, 366-369.

Lugal(e) ud melambi nirgal (3.1.y): Jacobsen, *The Harps that once ...* 233-272; Bottéro/Kramer, *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme* 339-377; *ETCSL* 1.6.2 (1998); G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 193-234; S. Seminara, *La versione accadica del Lugal-e (= MVS 8, 2001)*; Black et alii, *LAS* 163-180; W. Heimpel/E. Salgues, dans K. Volk (ed.), *Erzählungen aus dem Land Sumer* (2015) 33-67 et 417 sq. — Cf. Bruschiweiler, *Inanna* 66-74; J. van Dijk, *RIA* 7, 1/2 (1987) 134-136; W. Heimpel, *JNES* 46 (1987) 309-317; Th. Jacobsen, *Mél. Sachs* 225-232; F. Pomponio, *Formule di maledizione [...] (1990)* 81-83; G. Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 361 sq.; J. Black, *Mesopotamian Epic Literature* 76-86; W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT III/3* (1993) 435-448; Wilcke, *Politik und Literatur* 59 sq.; Penglase, *Greek Myths* 64-69; F.N.H. Al-Rawi, *Iraq* 57 (1995) 199-220 et appendice de A.R. George, *ibid.* 220-223.; K. Polinifer Foster, *HANE/M-III/3* (2000) 23-39; G.J. Selz, *Mél. Haas* (2001) 383-393; M. Streck, *Or.* 71 (2002) 217 sq.; C. Wilcke, in: M. Brehl/K. Platt (ed.), *Feindschaft* (2003) 113 sq.; F. Karahashi, *JEOL* 38 (2003-2004) 77-82; B. Groneberg, *Die Götter des Zweistromlandes* (2004) 81-85; Karahashi, *JNES* 63 (2004) 111-118; Seminara, *HSAO* 9 (2004) 243-250; Wagensooner, *Götterreisen* (2005) 132-134; Wilcke, *Anfänge* (2007) 11-13; A.M. Bagg, *Schriften der DWhG* 12 (2008) 219 sq.; J.-D. Forest, *Mém. Bottéro* 42-45; 47-53 passim; M.J. Geller, *Mém. Black* 93-100; L. Feldt, *OLA* 189 (2011) 123-163; E. Frahm, *GMTR* 5 (2011) 117-119; Y.S. Chen, *The Primeval Flood Catastrophe [...] (2013)* 77 sq.; Lisman, *At the beginning* (2013) 50 et 284-286 = *AOAT* 409 (2013) 53 et 310-313; K. Simkó, *JMC* 22 (2013) 24 sqq. passim; B. Böck, *The Healing Goddess Gula: Towards an Understanding of Ancient Babylonian Medicine (= CHANE 67, 2014)* 35-38; B.R. Foster,

CM 46 (2014) 51-56; K. Simkó, AoF 41 (2014) 112-124; I.A. Sviatopolk-Czetvertynski, AOAT 401 (2014) 779-993; L. Feldt, Numen 63 (2016) 357-364; M. Viano, The Reception of Sumerian Literature in the Western Periphery (2016) 90-95; J. Pace, Mythopoeia ou l'art de forger les "mythes" dans l'"aire culturelle" syro-mésopotamienne, méditerranéenne et indo-européenne (= SAAS 27, 2018) passim, surtout 75-101, 106-112, 118 sq., 129-209; K. Wagensonner, dans: J. Braarvig/M.J. Geller (ed.), Multilingualism, Lingua Franca and Lingua Sacra (Max Planck Research Library for the History and Development of Knowledge Studies 10, 2018) 248-256 et 280 sq.; M. Ramez, NABU 2018/110; A. Perdibon, LAOS 11 (2019) 47 sq.; M. Ramez, Mél. Charpin (2019) 862-866; W. Sallaberger, Tuna el-Gebel 9 (2019) 102-104; K. Simkó, NABU 2019/31.

Martu-Mythos (3.1.z): Bottéro/Kramer, Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme 430-437; W.H.Ph. Römer, UF 21 (1989) 319-334 (édition); S.N. Kramer, Mél. Artzi 11-27 (édition); Römer, TUAT III/3 (1993) 495-506; J. Klein, CM 7 (1997) 106-116 (édition); ETCSL 1.7.1 (1998); G. Pettinato, Mitologia sumerica (2001) 298-303; . — Cf. J.-J. Glassner dans B.S. Lesko (ed.), Women's Earliest Records [...] (= Brown Judaic Studies 166, Atlanta, Georgia, 1989) p. 77; Klein, Raphael Kutscher Memorial Volume 93-106; R. Rollinger, Nikephoros 7 (1994) 18-23; Klein, in M. Malul (ed.), Mutual Influences of Peoples and Cultures [...] (Haifa, 1996) 83-96; H.L.J. Vanstiphout, NABU 1996/54; id., OLA 96 (1999) 461-474; M. Streck, AOAT 271/1 (2000) 70-75 et Or. 71 (2002) 208 sq.; Y.S. Chen, The Primeval Flood Catastrophe [...] (2013) 92 sq.

Sargons-Legende (3.1.aa): V. Afanas²eva, AoF 14 (1987) 237-246; J.G. Westenholz, CM 7 (1997) 51-55 (VS 24 75); ETCSL 2.1.4 (1998); Black et alii, LAS 40-44; Attinger, TTS (2010, actualisé en 2015); J.L. Dahl/R.K. Englund, CDLI P469678 (2014); B.R. Foster, The Age of Agade: Inventing Empire in Ancient Mesopotamia (2016) 348-350. — Cf. J.S. Cooper dans A. Kort/S. Morschauser (ed.), Biblical and Related Studies Presented to Samuel Iwry (Winona Lake, 1985) 33-39; W.H.Ph. Römer, TUAT II/1 (1986) 31 sq.; B. Alster, ZA 77 (1987) 169-173; Cooper, HANES 5 (1993) 17 sq.; P. Attinger, NABU 1994/99; P. Gentili, Studi Cagni (2000) 355-373 passim, surtout 356-366; G. Cunningham, OLA 189 (2011) 81-96; M. Viano, The Reception of Sumerian Literature in the Western Periphery (2016) 44 sq.; P. Steinkeller, SANER 15 (2017) 182-186, 189-191.

Hymnen (3.2) P. Michalowski, Suppl. au Dict. de la Bible 72-73 (1999-2002) 255-262; C. Metcalf, The Gods Rich in Praise: Early Greek and Mesopotamian Religious Poetry (2015) passim, surtout 15-49 et 228-234.

Hendursanga-Hymne (3.2.1.a): ETCSL 4.06.1 (1999-2000); P. Attinger/M. Krebernik, AOAT 325 (2005) 21-104; F. Lara Peinado, Himnos sumerios (2006) 121-132; Attinger, TTS (2011, actualisé en 2015). — Cf. D.O. Edzard/C. Wilcke, AfO 25 (1974/1977) 36; H. Sauren, OLP 10 (1979) 75-95; T. Frymer-Kensky, In the Wake of the Goddesses (1992) 50-59; L. Verderame, AOAT 441 (2017) 283-285 et 293 sq.

Inannas Erhöhung (3.2.1.b): R. Labat, Les religions du Proche-Orient asiatique (Paris, 1970) 240-247; Castellino, TSA 107-114.; D. Foxvog, The Late Bilingual Exaltation of Ištar (Inannas Erhöhung), <http://berkeley.academia.edu/DanielFoxvog>, 2013. — Cf. W.G. Lambert, Or. 40 (1971) 91-95; E. von Weiher, ADFU 10 (1983) 136 Nr. 28; N. Veldhuis, AMD 13 (2018) 183-206.

Innin šagurra (3.2.1.c): ETCSL 4.07.3 (1999); Betty De Shong Meador, *Inanna, Lady of Largest Heart* (2000) 114-167 et 204-206; B.R. Foster, *The Age of Agade: Inventing Empire in Ancient Mesopotamia* (2016) 336-341; C. Halton/S. Svärd, *Women's Writing of Ancient Mesopotamia: An Anthology of the Earliest Female Authors* (2018) 79-87. — Cf. B. Alster, *NABU* 1990/100; Leick, *Sex and Eroticism* 59-63; Penglase, *Greek Myths* 45 sq.; P. Michalowski, in J. Braun et al. (ed.), *Written on Clay and Stone. Ancient Near Eastern Studies Presented to Krystyna Szarzynska on the Occasion of her 80th Birthday* (1998) 65-73; Broekema, *Inanna* (2013) 216-222; C.J. Crisostomo, *JANER* 15 (2015) 132-134; I. Peled, *AOAT* 435 (2016) 71-75; M. Viano, *The Reception of Sumerian Literature in the Western Periphery* (2016) 54-56.

Nanše-Hymne (3.2.1.d): Jacobsen, *The Harps that once ...* 125-142; M. Jacques, *Nanše, déesse de Lagaš (mémoire de licence, Univ. de Genève, 1989) annexe II* (transcription et traduction); W. Heimpel, *The Context of Scripture I* 526-531; ETCSL 4.14.1 (1998); F. Lara Peinado, *Himnos sumerios* (2006) 102-116; Attinger, *TTS* (2012, actualisé en 2015). — Cf. S.N. Kramer, *Mél. Finet* 78-80; K. Lämmerhirt, *AOAT* 348 (2010) 492-496, 576, 625 sq. et 898 (index des passages traduits).

Ninmešarra (3.2.1.e): A. Zgoll, *AOAT* 246 (1997) (édition); W.W. Hallo, *The Context of Scripture I* 518-522; ETCSL 4.07.2 (1999); Betty De Shong Meador, *Inanna, Lady of Largest Heart* (2000) 168-191 et 206-208; Black et alii, *LAS* 315-320; Delnero, *Variation* 2021-2108 (partition); F. Lara Peinado, *Himnos sumerios* (2006) 54-62; Attinger, *TTS* (2011, actualisé en 2015); Zgoll, *Enheduana singt gegen die drohende Vernichtung. Ein sumerisches Lied für ein gefährliches Ritual, von der frühesten Autorin der Weltliteratur*, dans: S. Franke (ed.), *Als die Götter Mensch waren* (2013) 77-87 et 119 sq.; ead., *TUAT NF* 8 (2015) 55-67; Zgoll, dans K. Volk (ed.), *Erzählungen aus dem Land Sumer* (2015) 339-350 et 436; B.R. Foster, *The Age of Agade: Inventing Empire in Ancient Mesopotamia* (2016) 331-336.; C. Halton/S. Svärd, *Women's Writing of Ancient Mesopotamia: An Anthology of the Earliest Female Authors* (2018) 93-98. — Cf. H. Sauren, *JEOL* 22 (1981/1982) 278-288; G. Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 367-369; Zgoll, *HANE/M III/2* (2000) 86-90.; S.G. Beld, *The Queen of Lagash: Ritual Economy in a Sumerian State* (Ph. D., University of Michigan 2002) 119-126; Zgoll, in: H. Felber (ed.) *Feinde und Aufrührer [...]* (2005) 294-300; Zgoll, in: R.G. Kratz/H. Spieckermann (ed.), *Götterbilder, Gottesbilder, Weltbilder. Polytheismus und Monotheismus in der Welt der Antike. Band I: Ägypten, Mesopotamien, Persien, Kleinasien, Syrien, Palästina* (Forschungen zum Alten Testament 2. Reihe Bd. 17, 2006) 115-124; A. Zgoll, in: J. Kügler/L. Bormann (ed.), *Töchter (Gottes). Studien zum Verhältnis von Kultur, Religion und Geschlecht. Bayreuther Forum* 8 (2008) 7-21, surtout 13-20; J.-J. Glassner, *Topoi Suppl.* 10 (2009) 225-228; J. Keetman, *AoF* 37 (2010) 38-48; Broekema, *Inanna* (2013) 206-215; E.S. Gerstenberger, *Theologie des Lobens in sumerischen Hymnen* (= *ORA* 28, 2018) 109-111; S. Helle, *Autorship* 8 (2019) 12-15.

Nisaba-Hymne (3.2.1.f): Castellino, *TSA* 84 sqq.; ETCSL 4.1.6.1 (1999-2000).

Enlil/Nippur-Hymne (3.2.3.a): Castellino, *TSA* 45 sqq.; Jacobsen, *The Harps that once ...* 101-111; ETCSL 4.05.1 (1998); Black et alii, *LAS* 320-325; Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 91-100; Delnero, *Variation* 2109-2172 (partition); Attinger, *TTS* (2014, actualisé en 2015) — Cf. H. Sauren, *JEOL* 22 (1971/1972) 272-278; S.N. Kramer, *BiMes.* 4 (1976) 4 sq.

Eridu-Hymne (3.2.3.b): Cf. Enkis Reise nach Nippur (3.1.p 1).

Keš-Hymne (3.2.3.c): Jacobsen, *The Harps that once ...* 377-385; ETCSL 4.80.2 (1999); Black et alii, *LAS* 326-330; Delnero, *Variation* 2173-2238 (partition); C. Wilcke, *CM* 35 (2006) 201-237.— Cf. M.J. Geller, *ZA* 86 (1996) 68-79; H. Steible, in: H.-J. Gehrke/A. Möller (ed.), *Vergangenheit und Lebenswelt [...]* (= *ScriptOralia* 90, 1996) 65-75.; M. Stol, *CM* 14 (2000) 76; P. Delnero, *The Textual Criticism of Sumerian Literature* (*JCS Suppl.* 3 [2012] 97-101; A. Zgoll, in: K. Schmid (ed.), *Schöpfung* (= *Themen der Theologie* 4, 2012) 27 sq.; E.S. Gerstenberger, *Theologie des Lobens in sumerischen Hymnen* (= *ORA* 28, 2018) 173-183.

Nungal-Hymne (3.2.3.d): G.R. Castellino, *Orientalis Antiqui Collectio* 13, *Atti del 1° convegno italiano sul vicino Oriente antico* (Roma, 22-24 Aprile 1976), Rome, 1978, pp. 9-23; ETCSL 4.28.1 (1999); P. Attinger, *Mél. Wilcke* (2003) 15-34 (édition); Black et alii, *LAS* 339-342; Delnero, *Variation* 2360-2395 (partition); Attinger, *TTS* (2011, actualisé en 2015). — Cf. B. Alster, *RA* 68 (1974) 60 n. 2; id., *AOAT* 25 (1976) 16 et n. 14; T.S. Frymer-Kensky, *JESHO* 20 (1977) 78-89; Å.W. Sjöberg, *JCS* 29 (1977) 3-6 et 32-35; W.W. Hallo, *JCS* 31 (1979) 161-165 (= *WOL* 583-588); Frymer-Kensky, *RA* 79 (1985) 93 sq.; Alster/C.B.F. Walker, *Mél. Sjöberg* 7-10; M. Civil, *Mél. Hallo* 72-74; A. Annus, *NABU* 2010/85; K. Lämmerhirt, *AOAT* 348 (2010) 499-501, 577, 627 sq. et 899 (index des passages cités); C. Ambos, *Der König im Gefängnis und das Neujahrfest im Herbst [...]* (2013) 76 sq. et 81-83; Oshima, T., *Babylonian Poems of Pious Sufferers* (*ORA* 14, 2014) 311-313; A. Jordanova, *Untersuchungen zur Gestalt einer Unterweltsgöttin: Ereškigal nach den sumerischen und akkadischen Quellentexten. Dissertation zur Erlangung des akademischen Grades Doctor Philosophiae (Dr. phil.), Universität Leipzig* (2015) 374 sq.; A. Annus, *SAAS* 24 (2016) 61-64.

Tempelbauhymne des Gudea von Lagaš (3.2.3.e): Averbeck, *Ritual avec litt. ant.* (transcription et traduction pp. 589-712); Jacobsen, *The Harps that once ...* 386-444; F. Lara Peinado, *Himno al Templo Eninnu. Cilindros A y B de Gudea* (1996); E.J. Wilson, *AOAT* 244 (1996) (édition); D.O. Edzard, *RIME* 3/1 (1997) (édition); ETCSL 2.1.7 (1998); Averbeck, *The Context of Scripture II* 415-433 (traduction partielle); W.H.P. Römer, *AOAT* 376 (2010) (édition); S. Paulus, *TUAT NF* 7 (2013) 9-35 (cylindre A); W. Heimpel, dans K. Volk (ed.), *Erzählungen aus dem Land Sumer* (2015) 119-165 et 420 sq. — Cf. C.E. Suter, *Gudea's Temple Building: A comparison of Written and Pictorial Accounts*, Ph. D., Univ. of Pennsylvania 1995; Averbeck in: G.D. Young/alii (eds.), *Crossing Boundaries and Linking Horizons. Studies in Honor of Michael C. Astour*, Bethesda 1997, 37-93; Suter, *ZA* 87 (1997) 1-10; B. Hruška, *AOAT* 267 (1999) 217-228; Kramer/Molina, *El Matrimonio Sagrado* 36-44; Suter, *Gudea's Temple Building: The Representation of an Early Mesopotamian Ruler in Text and Image* (= *CM* 17, 2000); Suter, in: P. Azara et alii (ed.), *Mites de fundació de ciutats al món antic (Mesopotàmia, grècia i Roma): actes del col.loqui* (*Monografies* 2, Barcelona 2001) 81-90, surtout 84-89; J. Polonsky, *The Rise of the Sun God and the Determination of Destiny in Ancient Mesopotamia* (PhD., Univ. of Philadelphia 2002) 642-678 (index des passages cités pp. 1101f.); J.-J. Glassner, *Mél. H. et M. Tadmor* (2003) 62*-69*; G. Pettinato, *Il rituale della costruzione del tempio Eninnu nei cilindri di Gudea di Lagaš*, dans: *La casa del dio. Il tempio nella cultura del Vicino Oriente Antico. Atti del Convegno internazionale Milano, 31 gennaio 2004* (2005) 31-52; Black et alii, *LAS* 44-52 (traduction partielle); B. Pongratz-Leisten, *BaM* 37 (2006) 45-59; A. Nagy, *NABU* 2007/35; A.R. Øiseth, *With roots*

in the Abzu and crown in the sky: Temple construction in between myth and reality – A study of the Eninnu temple of the Gudea cylinders as divine house and cosmic link. A dissertation presented to Institutt for Kulturstudier at the University of Oslo, for partial fulfilment of the degree of Master in History of Religion, 2007; Averbeck, AOAT 366 (2010) 3-34 passim; S. Anthonioz, Babel la tête dans le ciel, Suppl. n° 20 à Transeuphratène (2015) 23-28; P. Steinkeller, dans: P. Steinkeller/M. Hudson (ed.), *Labor in the Ancient World* (2015) 146-153; C. Metcalf, dans: E.J. Hamori/J. Stökl (ed.), *Perchance to Dream: Dream Divination in the Bible and the Ancient Near East* (2018) 10-15; R.E. Averbeck, AOAT 460 (2020) 79-100.

Tempelliederzyklus (3.2.3.f): ETCSL 4.80.1 (1998-1999); Vanstiphout, Eduba (2004) 123-133; B.D.S. Meador, *Princess, Priestess, Poet: the Sumerian Temple Hymns of Enheduanna* (2009); C. Halton/S. Svärd, *Women's Writing of Ancient Mesopotamia: An Anthology of the Earliest Female Authors* (2018) 53-79. — Cf. Kramer/Maier, *Myths of Enki* 94 sq.; W.H.Ph. Römer, TUAT II/5 (1989) 686-688; J.A. Black, NABU 2002/4; F. Lara Peinado, *Himnos sumerios* (2006) 234-236; V.A. Hurowitz, *Mél. Abusch* (2010) 70-74; 77-79; V.K. Afanasieva, BaBi. 8 (2014) 1-9; A. Jordanova, *Untersuchungen zur Gestalt einer Unterweltsgöttin: Ereškigal nach den sumerischen und akkadischen Quellentexten. Dissertation zur Erlangung des akademischen Grades Doctor Philosophiae (Dr. phil.), Universität Leipzig* (2015) 375 sq.; P. Espak, *Melammu 2* (2019) 18 sq.; S. Helle, *Autorship 8* (2019) 9-12; A. Johandi, *The God Asar/Asalluḫi in the Early Mesopotamian Pantheon (Dissertationes Theologiae Universitatis Tartuensis 37, 2019)* 81-88; J. Peterson, JCS 72 (2020) 129 sqq.

Preis der Hacke (3.2.4): G. Farber, *The Context of Scripture I* 511-513; ETCSL 5.5.4 (2000-2001); Black et alii, LAS 311-315; Vanstiphout, Eduba (2004) 82-90; Delnero, *Variation 2021-2108* (partition); G. Farber, dans K. Volk (ed.), *Erzählungen aus dem Land Sumer* (2015) 69-76 et 418; C. Halton/S. Svärd, *Women's Writing of Ancient Mesopotamia: An Anthology of the Earliest Female Authors* (2018) 46-50. — Cf. M.-J. Seux, dans Seux et al., *La création et le déluge d'après les textes du Proche-Orient ancien (Supplément au Cahier Evangile 64 [1988])* 22-24; Bottéro/Kramer, *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme* 508-511; G. Farber, BBVO 18 (1999) 369-373; G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 416 sq.; M. Dietrich, MARG 16 (2004) 23 sq.; id., MARG 17 (2005) 139-141; Wilcke, *Anfänge* (2007) 28 sq.; P. Michalowski, *Mél. Owen* (2010) 195-200; Y.S. Chen, *The Primeval Flood Catastrophe [...] (2013) sq.*; Lisman, *At the beginning* (2013) 55-57 et 296-304 = AOAT 409 (2013) 57-59 et 324-329; E.S. Gerstenberger, *Theologie des Lobens in sumerischen Hymnen (= ORA 28, 2018)* 183-187.

Klagelied(er) (3.4.): Cf. W.W. Hallo, in: J.M. Sasson (ed.), *Civilizations of the Ancient Near East III* (1995) 1871-1881; A. Löhnert, *Motive und Funktionen der Göttinnenklagen im Frühen Mesopotamien*, OBO 251 (2011) 39-62; ead., *Manipulating the Gods: Lamenting in Context*, dans: K. Radner and E. Robson (ed.), *The Oxford Handbook of Cuneiform Culture* (2011) 402-417; N. Samet, *Encyclopedia of the Bible and Its Reception 15* (2017) 687-691.

Historische Klage (3.4.1): Cf. H.L.J. Vanstiphout, BBVO 6 (1986) 1-11; P. Mander, *Mél. Moscati* (1996) I 261-269; B. Lion, *Âges d'or et paradis perdus dans la littérature sumérienne*, dans: V. Pirenne-Delforge et Ö. Tunca (ed.), *Représentations du temps dans les religions. Actes du Colloque organisé par le Centre d'Histoire des Religions de l'Université de Liège* (2003) 68-72; J.S. Cooper, JCS 58 (2006) 39-47; G. Rubio, *Sumerian Literature*, in:

C.S. Ehrlich (ed.), *From an Antique Land [...]* (2009) 62 sq.; D.L. Petter, OBO 246 (2011) 7-33 passim; I. Slobodzianek, *Acquérir, exprimer et transmettre les "pouvoirs" divins: une comparaison entre Aphrodite et Inanna/Ištar*, thèse de doctorat, Toulouse 2012 (<https://de.scribd.com/document/135631970/Acquerir-exprimer-et-transmettre-les-pouvoirs-divins-Une-comparaison-entre-Aphrodite-et-Inanna-Istar>) 276-279; N. Samet, MC 18 (2014) 1-13; U. Gabbay, *Pacifying the Hearts of the Gods [...]* (= HES 1, 2014) 13 sq.; C. Bonnet/I. Slobodzianek, *De la steppe au bateau céleste ou comment Inanna accomplit son destin entre mythe et rite*, dans: N. Belayche/V. Pirenne-Delforge, *Fabriquer du divin. Constructions et ajustements de la représentation des dieux dans l'Antiquité* (2015) 29-34; J. Jacobs, *The city lament genre in the ancient Near East*, dans: M.R. Bachvarova et al. (ed.), *The Fall of Cities in the Mediterranean: Commemoration in Literature, Folk-Song, and Liturgy* (2016) 13-35.

Eridu-Klage (3.4.1.a): ETCSL 2.2.6 (1998). — Cf. Rollinger, *Frühformen* 217 sq.; I. Peled, JCS 67 (2015) 39-43; H. Schaudig, *dubsar* 13 (2019) 283 sq.

Nippur-Klage (3.4.1.b): S.N. Kramer, ASJ 13 (1991) 1-26 (édition); St. Tinney, *Nippur Lament: Royal Rhetoric and Divine Legitimation in the Reign of Isme-Dagan of Isin (1953-1935 B.C.)*, OPSNKF 16,1996 (édition); ETCSL 2.2.4 (1998-1999); Attinger, TTS (2010, actualisé en 2015); J.L. Dahl/R.K. Englund, CDLI (2014-2015). — Cf. Rollinger, *Frühformen* 218-222; H.L.J. Vanstiphout, RIA 9/7-8 (2001) 565 sq.; I. Slobodzianek, *Acquérir, exprimer et transmettre les "pouvoirs" divins: une comparaison entre Aphrodite et Inanna/Ištar*, thèse de doctorat, Toulouse 2012 (<https://de.scribd.com/document/135631970/Acquerir-exprimer-et-transmettre-les-pouvoirs-divins-Une-comparaison-entre-Aphrodite-et-Inanna-Istar>) 275-279; N. Samet, MC 18 (2014) 1-13 passim; C. Bonnet/I. Slobodzianek, *De la steppe au bateau céleste ou comment Inanna accomplit son destin entre mythe et rite*, dans: N. Belayche/V. Pirenne-Delforge, *Fabriquer du divin. Constructions et ajustements de la représentation des dieux dans l'Antiquité* (2015) 29-33; H. Schaudig, *dubsar* 13 (2019) 284 sq.

Klage über Sumer und Ur (3.4.1.c): P. Michalowski, *The Lamentation over the Destruction of Sumer and Ur (= Mesopotamian Civilizations 1, Winona Lake, 1989) avec litt. ant.* (édition); ETCSL 2.2.3 (1998); Black et alii, LAS 127-141; Attinger, TTS (2009, actualisé en 2015); C.B. Hays, *Hidden Riches: A Sourcebook for the Comparative Study of the Hebrew Bible and Ancient Near East* (2014) 375-396 (traduction de P. Michalowski 1989, commentaire). — Cf. W.H.Ph. Römer, TUAT II/5 (1989) 700-707; Rollinger, *Frühformen* 207-216; Wilcke, *Politik und Literatur* 36; Kramer/Molina, *El Matrimonio Sagrado* 62 sq.; C. Wilcke, in: D. Hoffmann (ed.), *Vermächtnis der Abwesenheit. Spuren traumatisierender Ereignisse in der Kunst* (2000) 74-78 (traduction partielle); J. Kinnier-Wilson, *Iraq* 67 (2005) 49-56 passim; B. Studevent-Hickman, dans: M.W. Chavalas (ed.), *The Ancient Near East* (2006) 67-72; J.L. Dahl, PIHANS 108 (2011) 55-65 (v. à ce propos P. Attinger, NABU 2011/56); Broekema, *Inanna* (2013) 273-277; Y.S. Chen, *The Primeval Flood Catastrophe [...]* (2013) 96 sq.; N. Samet, MC 18 (2014) 1-13 passim; H. Schaudig, *dubsar* 13 (2019) 269-277.

Klage über die Zerstörung von Ur (3.4.1.d): M. Witzel, Or. 14 (1945) 185-234 et Or. 15 (1946) 46-63 (édition); Y. Rosengarten, RHR 174 (1968) 117-160; id., *Trois aspects de la pensée religieuse sumérienne* (Paris, 1971) 43-132; Castellino, TSA 283-301; Jacobsen, *The Harps that once ...* 447-474; ETCSL 2.2.2 (1998); W.H.P. Römer, AOAT 309 (2004) (édition); N. Samet, *The Lamentation over the Destruction of Ur*. MC 18, 2014 (édition); Attinger, TTS 2014; J.L. Dahl/K. Englund, CDLI (2014-2015). — Cf. J. Krecher, ZA 60

(1970) 202 sq.; H. Sauren, JNES 29 (1970) 42-47; G. Pettinato, I Sumeri (1991) 301 sq.; Rollinger, Frühformen 216 sq.; J. Klein, The Context of Scripture I 535-539 (traduction partielle); C. Wilcke, in: D. Hoffmann (ed.), Vermächtnis der Abwesenheit. Spuren traumatisierender Ereignisse in der Kunst (2000) 71-74 (traduction partielle); D.E. Fleming, The Classical World 97 (2003) 5-18 passim; J. Kinnier-Wilson, Iraq 67 (2005) 51-58 passim; N. Samet, NABU 2010/62 (joins et nouvelles lectures); P. Attinger, NABU 2011/57; A. Löhnert, JCS 63 (2011) 65-72 (édition d'un nouveau duplicat); N. Samet and S.F. Adalı, JCS 64 (2012) 31-37 (nouveaux duplicats, traduction partielle); P. Attinger, Or. 84 (2015) 41-74 ("review-article" de Samet 2014); J. Jacobs, dans: M.R. Bachvarova et al. (ed.), The Fall of Cities in the Mediterranean: Commemoration in Literature, Folk-Song, and Liturgy (2016) 25-30; L. Vacín, ArOr. 85 (2017) 461-478 ("review-article" de Samet 2014); H. Schaudig, dubsar 13 (2019) 279-283.

Uruk-Klage (3.4.1.e): ETCSL 2.2.5 (1998). A. Cavigneaux, ZA 103 (2013) 4-15. — Cf. Rollinger, Frühformen 222-226; J. Polonsky, The Rise of the Sun God and the Determination of Destiny in Ancient Mesopotamia (PhD., Univ. of Philadelphia 2002) 704-709, N. Samet, MC 18 (2014) 1-13 passim; H. Schaudig, dubsar 13 (2019) 278 sq.

Klage über die Zerstörung der Heiligtümer von Lagaš (3.4.1.f): W.H.Ph. Römer, TUAT I/4 (1984) 313-315; J.S. Cooper, Sumerian and Akkadian Royal Inscriptions, I: Presargonic Inscriptions (New Haven 1986) 78-79. D.R. Frayne, RIME 1 (2008) 276-279 (édition). — Cf. F. Pomponio, Formule di maledizione della Mesopotamia preclassica (Brescia 1990) 20; G. Pettinato, I Sumeri (Milano 1991) 234-235; J. Krecher, Gs. Kutscher (1993) 114-117 (i 6-9 //); M.A. Powell, WZKM 86 (1996) 307-314; G. Cunningham, StPohl SM 17 (1997) 47-48 (vii 10-ix 3); J. Bauer, OBO 160/1 (1998) 489-493.

Persönliche Klage (3.4.4): Cf. M. Jaques, Metaphern als Kommunikationsstrategie in den mesopotamischen Bußgebeten an den persönlichen Gott, OBO 251 (2011) 3-19; ead., OBO 273 (2015).

Der Mensch und sein Gott (3.4.4): W.H.Ph. Römer, TUAT III/1 (1990) 102-109; ETCSL 5.2.4 (1998-1999); Vanstiphout, Eduba (2004) 270-277. — Cf. J. van Dijk, SSA 122-127; id. dans J.P. Asmussen/*alii* (ed.), Handbuch der Religionsgeschichte I (Göttingen, 1971) 493-496; S.N. Kramer, BiMes. 4 (1976) 10 sq.; J. Klein, AfO Bh. 19 (1982) 297-306; G.L. Mattingly dans W.W. Hallo, B.W. Jones and G.L. Mattingly (ed.), The Bible in the Light of Cuneiform Literature: Scripture In Context III (= Ancient Near Eastern Texts and Studies 8, 1990) 305-348; D. Sitzler, Vorwurf gegen Gott (= Studies in Oriental Religions 32, 1995) 61-71; Klein, The Context of Scripture I 573-575 (traduction partielle); H. Limet, Transeuphratène 22 (2001) 117 sq.; O. Loretz, AOAT 290 (2003) 188-190; Klein, CM 35 (2006) 123-143; C. Uehlinger, dans: T. Krüger et al. (ed.), Das Buch Hiob und seine Interpretationen. Beiträge zum Hiob-Symposium auf dem Monte Verità vom 14.-19. August 2005 (2007) 128-132; S. Fink, Kaskal 9 (2012) 77 sq.; T. Oshima, ORA 14 (2014) 19-22; M. Jaques, OBO 273 (2015) 4-10; N. Ziegler, OBO 278 (2015) 219 sq.

Briefe an Götter (3.5.1): ETCSL 3.3/... (2001). — Cf. B. Böck, AoF 23 (1996) 3-23; B. Pongratz-Leisten, SAAS 10 (1999) 213-217; D. Bodi, Ktama 33 (2008) 246-249; A. Kleinerman, CM 42 (2011) 35-37; A. Löhnert, WO 44 (2014) 203-208.

Königsbriefe (3.5.2): ETCSL 3.1/... et 3.2/... (2001). A. Kleinerman, *Education in Early 2nd Millennium BC Babylonia*. CM 42, 2011; P. Michalowski, *The Correspondence of the Kings of Ur*. MC 15, 2011; Attinger, TTS (ANL 7, 9 [2013-2014]; CKU 1, 2, 4, 8, 18, 21, 23, 24 [2012]; SEpM 2, 4-7, 16-19 [2013]). — Cf. F. Huber, ZA 91 (2001) 169-206; P. Michalowski, *Suppl. au Dict. de la Bible* 73 (2002) 262-267; Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 58-68; W.W. Hallo, CM 35 (2006) 85-104 (= WOL 385-405); P. Michalowski, dans: M.W. Chavalas (ed.), *The Ancient Near East* (2006) 75-81; A. Kleinerman, *Kaskal* 5 (2008) 173-186; P. Michalowski, dans: A. Feldherr and G. Hardy (ed.), *The Oxford History of Historical Writing I: Beginnings to AD 600* (2011) 18-20; F. Huber Vulliet, dans: K. Radner and E. Robson (ed.), *The Oxford Handbook of Cuneiform Culture* (2011) 486-507, surtout 489 sqq.

(*Epische*) *Streitgespräche* (3.6.1.): Cf. en général B. Alster dans E. Keck/*alii* (ed.), *Living Waters ... Presented to F. Løkkegaard* (Copenhagen, 1990) 1-16 avec litt. ant.; H.L.J. Vanstiphout, ASJ 12 (1990) 271-318 avec litt. ant.; id., OLA 42 (1991) 23-46; id., ASJ 14 (1992) 339-367; ID, *Res Orientales IV* (1992) 12-21; S. Ponchia, *La palma e il tamarisco e altri dialoghi mesopotamici* (Venise 1996); Alster, *Suppl. au Dict. de la Bible* 73 (2002) 288-291; D.O. Edzard, OBO 160/4 (2004) 524 sq.; Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 153-203; S. Herrmann, *Saeculum* 59 (2008) 201-212; ead., *Vogel und Fisch*; E. Jiménez, CHANE 87 (2017) 13-26. — Ein sumerisches Rangstreitgespräch. Textedition und Kommentar (2010) 17-95; M. Lang, *Sieg und Nicht-Sieg in altorientalischen Streitgedichten*, dans: M. Fahlenbock / L. Madersbacher / I. Schneider (ed.), *Inszenierung des Sieges — Sieg der Inszenierung. Interdisziplinäre Perspektiven* (Innsbruck 2011) 69-77; K. Volk, RIA 13/3-4 (2012) 214-222 s.v. *Streitgespräch*; H. Vanstiphout, CM 46 (2014) 229-240; F. Kilchör/C. Mittermayer, CRRAI 61 (2018) 225-240; L. Vacín, CRRAI 61 (2018) 447-457; C. Mittermayer, UAVA 15 (2019) passim.

Edelmetall und Kupfer (3.6.1.a): ETCSL 5.3.6 (2000). — Cf. H.L.J. Vanstiphout, OLA 42 (1991) 26 n. 17 (bibl.); Wilcke, *Anfänge* (2007) 23 sq./47; E. Jiménez, CHANE 87 (2017) 23; L. Vacín, CRRAI 61 (2018) 449.

Enmerkar und En-MÛŠ-kéšda-anna (3.6.1.b): ETCSL 1.8.2.4 (1998); H. Vanstiphout, *Helden en goden van Sumer* (1998) 68-83; Black et alii, LAS 3-11; Vanstiphout, *Epics of Sumerian Kings: The Matter of Aratta* (= *Writings from the Ancient World* 20, 2004) 23-48; G. Pettinato, *Dal mare alla montagna dei cedri. Il poema sumerico di Enmerkar ed Ensuhgiranna* (2006), surtout 66-126; Attinger, TTS (2008, actualisé en 2015); C. Wilcke, *The Sumerian Poem Enmerkar and En-suḫkeš-ana: Epic, Play, Or? [...]*. AOS Essay 12, 2012; C. Mittermayer/P. Attinger, *Enmerkara und Ensukukešdana*, dubsar 17 (2020) 191-262. — Cf. W. Heimpel, JAOS 101 (1981) 404-407; H. Behrens, AfO 29-30 (1983/1984) 98-103; G. Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 151-153; Attinger, *Eléments* 36 (reconstruction du texte); Vanstiphout, OLP 26 (1995) 5-20; M. Streck, Or. 71 (2002) 212 sq.; G. Zólyomi, NABU 2003/61 (reconstruction du texte); D. Schwemer, *Abwehrzauber und Behexung. Studien zum Schadenzauberglauben im alten Mesopotamien* (2008) 135-137; Vanstiphout, *Gs. Black* 361-377 passim; C. Mittermayer, ORA 10 (2013) 32-34; F. Hazelton, *Three Kings of Warka: Enmerkar, Lugalbanda, Gilgamesh. Myths from Mesopotamia* (2013) 1-10 (renarration); M. Ceccarelli, *Fabula* 58 (2017) 376-378 (à propos des ll. 171-183, 197-199); L. Vacín, CRRAI 61 (2018) 448 sq.; M. Ceccarelli, *Fabula* 60 (2019) 107-110 (à propos des ll. 224-271); C. Mittermayer, UAVA 15 (2019) 11.

Hacke und Pflug (3.6.1.c): H.L.J. Vanstiphout, *The Context of Scripture I* 578-581; ETCSL 5.3.1 (2000); Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 156-167; D.O. Edzard, *OBO* 160/4 (2004) 525-531 (translit. et traduction partielles); Attinger, *TTS* (2010, actualisé en 2015); C. Mittermayer, *UAVA* 15 (2019) 1-36 passim, 109-137, 139-161 passim, 285-354 (édition). — Cf. Hruška, *Ackerbau* 495-499; S. Herrmann, *Vogel und Fisch — Ein sumerisches Rangstreitgespräch. Textedition und Kommentar* (2010) 45-47; 76 sq.; 91 sq.; 93 sq.; E. Jiménez, *CHANE* 87 (2017) 17; R. Pientka-Hinz, dans: J. Renn et al. (ed.), *Wissensgeschichte der Architektur Band I: vom Neolithikum bis zum Alten Orient* (2017) 297-299; L. Vacín, *CRRAI* 61 (2018) 447 sq. avec n. 10, 452.

Holz und Rohr (3.6.1.d): Cf. J. van Dijk, *ActOr.* 28 (1964/1965) 44-57; Bottéro/Kramer, *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme* 479-481; W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT III/3* (1993) 357-360; G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 100-103; Wilcke, *Anfänge* (2007) 19 sq./46; S. Herrmann, *Vogel und Fisch — Ein sumerisches Rangstreitgespräch. Textedition und Kommentar* (2010) 43 et 70-95 passim; Lisman, *At the beginning* (2013) 38 sq. et 229-233 = *AOAT* 409 (2013) 39 sq. et 251-255; E. Jiménez, *CHANE* 87 (2017) 20 sq.; L. Vacín, *CRRAI* 61 (2018) 452-455.

Mutterschaf und Getreide (3.6.1.e): B. Alster/H.L.J. Vanstiphout, *ASJ* 9 (1987) 1-43 avec litt. ant. (édition); Vanstiphout, *The Context of Scripture I* 575-578 (traduction partielle); Black et alii, *LAS* 225-229; ETCSL 5.3.2 (1999-2000); Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 186-194; C. Mittermayer, *UAVA* 15 (2019) 1-36 passim, 37-66, 139-161 passim, 163-227 (édition). — Cf. J. Bauer, *AfO Bh.* 19 (1982) 377-383; M.-J. Seux, dans Seux et al., *La création et le déluge d'après les textes du Proche-Orient ancien (Supplément au Cahier Evangile 64 [1988])* 40 sq.; Bottéro/Kramer, *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme* 511-514; Hruška, *Ackerbau* 499-505; G. Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 325 sq. et 378 sq.; H.L.J. Vanstiphout, *Res Orientales IV* (1992) 18-21; Kramer/Molina, *El Matrimonio Sagrado* 67 sq.; G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 427-429; M. Tanret, *Mél. Klener* (2004) 186-191; Wilcke, *Anfänge* (2007) 22 sq.; J. Marzahn, dans: J. Marzahn und G. Schauerte (ed.), *Babylon: Wahrheit* (2008) 234 sq.; S. Herrmann, *Vogel und Fisch — Ein sumerisches Rangstreitgespräch. Textedition und Kommentar* (2010) 70-95 passim; M. Dietrich, *MARG* 20 (2010) 40-44; A. Schellenberg, *Der Mensch, das Bild Gottes? Zum Gedanken einer Sonderstellung des Menschen im Alten Testament und in weiteren altorientalischen Quellen* *AThANT* 101, (2011) 261-269; A. Zgoll, in: K. Schmid (ed.), *Schöpfung (= Themen der Theologie 4, 2012)* 60-62; Y.S. Chen, *The Primeval Flood Catastrophe [...]* (2013) 88-90; Lisman, *At the beginning* (2013) 39-42 et 234-257 = *AOAT* 409 (2013) 40-44 et 256-281; E. Jiménez, *CHANE* 87 (2017) 17-19; F. Kilchör/C. Mittermayer, *CRRAI* 61 (2018) 225-240 passim.

Reiher und Schildkröte (3.6.1.f): T.J.H. Krispijn, dans: W.L. Idema et al. (ed.), *"Mijn naam is haas." Dierenverhalten in verschillende culturen* (1993) 144-148; G.B. Gragg, *The Context of Scripture I* 571-573; ETCSL 5.9.2 (1999-2000); Black et alii, *LAS* 235-240; Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 179-186; Peterson, *Faunal Conception* (2007) 269-410 (édition). — Cf. S. Herrmann, *Vogel und Fisch — Ein sumerisches Rangstreitgespräch. Textedition und Kommentar* (2010) 53 sq.; C. Mittermayer, *UAVA* 15 (2019) 11.

Sommer und Winter (3.6.1.g): H.L.J. Vanstiphout, *The Context of Scripture I* 584-588; ETCSL 5.3.3 (1999-2000); Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 167-179. — Cf. Bottéro/Kramer, *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme* 481-483; Vanstiphout, *ASJ* 14 (1992) 339 sqq., surtout 348-352; Peterson, *Faunal Conception* 468-487 (ll. 69-79); Wilcke, *Anfänge* (2007) 18 sq./44

sq.; S. Herrmann, *Vogel und Fisch — Ein sumerisches Rangstreitgespräch. Textedition und Kommentar* (2010) 41 sq. et 70-95 passim; E. Jiménez, *CHANE* 87 (2017) 19 sq.; L. Vacín, *CRRAI* 61 (2018) 450-452.

Vogel und Fisch (3.6.1.h): *ETCSL* 5.3.5 (1999-2000); Black et alii, *LAS* 230-235; Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 194-203; S. Herrmann, *Vogel und Fisch — Ein sumerisches Rangstreitgespräch. Textedition und Kommentar* (2010); C. Mittermayer, *UAVA* 15 (2019) 1-36 passim, 67-97, 139-161 passim, 228-284 (édition). — S.N. Kramer, *CRRAI* 11 (1962, ed. 1964) 96-101; id., *Phoenix* 10 (1964) 102-108; T.J.H. Krispijn, dans: W.L. Idema et al. (ed.), "Mijn naam is haas." *Dierenverhalten in verschillende culturen* (1993) 138-144; H.L.J. Vanstiphout, *The Context of Scripture I* 581-584; C. Mittermayer, *mušen ku₆: Viel Vogel und wenig Fisch in MS 2110/1, AoF* 41 (2014) 201-222 (édition partielle). — Cf. Bottéro/Kramer, *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme* 517-519; Kramer/Maier, *Myths of Enki* 86 sq.; G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 115 sq.; Wilcke, *Anfänge* (2007) 20 sq.; J. C. Johnson, *AoF* 37 (2010) 230-241; E. Jiménez, *CHANE* 87 (2017) 21 sq.; F. Kilchör/C. Mittermayer, *CRRAI* 61 (2018) 225-240 passim; ead. in R. Mattila et al. (ed.), *Animals and their Relation to Gods, Humans and Things in the Ancient World* (2019) 175-186.

Hirte und Bauer (3.6.1.i): *SRT* 3 // (Dumuzi et Enkimdu) n'est pas la suite de BE 30 4 (= PBS 1/1 6) // (Dumuzi-Inanna A).

a) Dumuzi-Inanna A²: Sefati, *Love Songs* 120-127 avec litt. ant. (édition); Jacobsen, *The Harps that once ...* 13-15; *ETCSL* 4.08.01 (1998); Black et alii, *LAS* 206-209; P. Mander, *Canti sumerici d'amore e morte (Testi del Vicino Oriente antico 2/8, 2005)* 106-109; Attinger, *TTS* (2010, actualisé en 2015). — Cf. Kramer/Molina, *El Matrimonio Sagrado* 81-83 et 182 sq.; M.M. Fritz, *AOAT* 307 (2003) 82; P. Lapinkivi, *SAAS* 15 (2004) 31 sq.; M.E. Couto-Ferreira, *SANER* 12 (2017) 62 sq.

b) Dumuzi et Enkimdu: Sefati, *Love Songs* 324-343 avec litt. ant. (édition); *ETCSL* 4.08.33 (1999); Black et alii, *LAS* 86-88; P. Mander, *Canti sumerici d'amore e morte (Testi del Vicino Oriente antico 2/8, 2005)* 114-118; Attinger, *TTS* (2010, actualisé en 2015). — Cf. P. Attinger, *NABU* 1996/110; Kramer/Molina, *El Matrimonio Sagrado* 70 et 84-86 et 183; M.M. Fritz, *AOAT* 307 (2003) 88; C. Mittermayer, *BaBi.* 8 (2014) 383-397; ead., *UAVA* 15 (2019) 10 sq.

Schulstreitgespräche (3.6.2): Cf. en général K. Volk, *Saeculum* 47 (1996) 178-216; *ZA* 90 (2000) 1-30; B. Alster, *Suppl. au Dict. de la Bible* 73 (2002) 291-293; Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 219 sq.; K. Volk, *RIA* 13/3-4 (2012) 220-222.

Streit zweier Schulabsolventen ("Dialogue 1") (3.6.2.a): J. Cale Johnson and M.J. Geller, *CM* 47 (2015) (édition).

Enkitalu und Enki-ḫegal ("Dialogue 2") (3.6.2.b). Cf. M. Ceccarelli, *OaF* 45 (2018) 133-155 passim.

Enki-mansum und Girine-isa ("Dialogue 3") (3.6.2.c): Cf. W.H.Ph. Römer, *UF* 20 (1988) 233-245 avec litt. ant. (édition partielle); id., *TUAT* III/1 (1990) 91-98; H.L.J.

² L'incipit est ^rses⁷-e nin₉-ra.

Vanstiphout, *The Context of Scripture I* 589-590 (traduction partielle); Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 218-224. — Cf. M. Ceccarelli, *OaF* 45 (2018) 133-155 *passim*.

Der Schreiber und sein 'Aufseher' ("Dialogue 4") (3.6.2.d): H.L.J. Vanstiphout, *The Context of Scripture I* 590-592 (traduction partielle); ETCSL 5.1.3 (2000); C. Wilcke, in: R. Lux (ed.), *Schau auf die Kleinen ...* [...] (Leipzig 2002) 23-30; Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 224-229; K. Volk, dans K. Volk (ed.), *Erzählungen aus dem Land Sumer* (2015) 109-116 et 420.

"Edubbâ Regulations" (3.6.2.e): Cf. M. Civil, *Mél. Birot* 73 n.4.

Streit zweier Frauen ("Dialogue 5") (3.6.2.f) Cf. K. Volk, *ZA* 90 (2000) 16-20.

Schulsatiren (3.6.3): Cf. en général K. Volk, *Saeculum* 47 (1996) 178-216; B. Alster, *Suppl. au Dict. de la Bible* 73 (2002) 291-293; C. Wilcke, in: R. Lux (ed.), *Schau auf die Kleinen ...* [...] (Leipzig 2002) 10-31; Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 205-219, 235-244.

Der Sohn des 'Tafelhauses' (3.6.3.a): W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT III/1* (1990) 68-77; D.O. Edzard, *OBO* 160/4 (2004) 531-539 (édition); Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 206-211; Attinger, *TTS* (2009, actualisé en 2015); K.S. Schmidt, *Aus dem Leben eines Schülers*, dans: S. Franke (ed.), *Als die Götter Mensch waren* (2013) 110-114 et 122; R.K. Englund, *CDLI P464238* (2014); K. Volk, dans K. Volk (ed.), *Erzählungen aus dem Land Sumer* (2015) 101-107 et 420. — Cf. C. Wilcke, in: R. Lux (ed.), *Schau auf die Kleinen ...* [...] (Leipzig 2002) 17-19; Peterson, J., *AulOr.* 33 (2015) 93 sq.

Der Vater und sein mißratener Sohn (3.6.3.b): W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT III/1* (1990) 77-91; Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 211-219. — Cf. B. Alster, *RA* 69 (1975) 81-84; C. Wilcke, in: R. Lux (ed.), *Schau auf die Kleinen ...* [...] (Leipzig 2002) 19-23.

Examenstext A (3.7.1.a): Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 238-243. — Cf. J.A. Black, *StPohl SM* 12 (1984) 72-74.

Examenstext D (3.7.1.b): W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT III/1* (1990) 46-48; Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 243 sq. — Cf. G. Pettinato, *I Sumeri* (1991) 350; V.A. Hurowitz, *JANES* 27 (2000) 49-56.

Unterweisungen eines Bauern an seinen Sohn (3.7.1.c): M. Civil, *The Farmer's Instructions* [...] (= *AulOr. Suppl.* 5, 1994); ETCSL 5.6.3 (1999); Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 117-123. — Cf. Th. Jacobsen, *BiMes.* 14 (1982) 56-60; Hruška, *Ackerbau* 491-495; A. Cavigneaux, *AulOr.* 9 (1991) 37-46; Hruška, *ZDMG Suppl.* 10 (1994) 23-31; E.S. Gerstenberger, *Theologie des Lobens in sumerischen Hymnen* (= *ORA* 28, 2018) 136-141.

Unterweisungen des Šuruppag an seinen Sohn Ziusudra (3.7.1.d): W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT III/1* (1990) 48-67; ETCSL 5.6.1 (1999); Black et alii, *LAS* 284-292; B. Alster, *Wisdom of Ancient Sumer* (2005) 31-220 und pl. 1-15, 17-29 und 60-69 (édition). — Cf. B. Alster, *AulOr.* 5 (1987) 199-206; M. Civil, *ib.* 207-210; Alster, *ZA* 80 (1990) 15-19; id., dans: A. Assmann (ed.), *Weisheit* [...] (München, 1991) 103-115, surtout 103-109; J.R. Davila, *JNES* 54 (1995) 202; Alster, *The Context of Scripture I* 569-570 (traduction

partielle); Alster, dans: K. Eksell/L. Feldt (ed.), *Readings in Eastern Mediterranean Literatures* (2006) 46-49 (traduction partielle); Gadotti, *Sumerian wisdom literature* 62-64, 70 sq.; Y.S. Chen, *The Primeval Flood Catastrophe [...]* (2013) 8 sq., 101-103, 132-139; J. Fechner, *Moral Concepts within the Sumerian-Akkadian Proverbial Literature: Origins, Developments and Tendencies*, dans: M-S. Ortola/G. Achard-Bayle (ed.), *Cocepts éthiques et moraux: approches multiculturelles et interdisciplinaires. Sémantique des énoncés parémiques* (2015) 21-25; J. Klein/N. Samet, *Mél. Hurowitz* (2015) 299-303; B.R. Foster, *The Age of Agade: Inventing Empire in Ancient Mesopotamia* (2016) 210-212/224 sq.; M. Viano, *The Reception of Sumerian Literature in the Western Periphery* (2016) 57 sq.; W. Sallaberger, dans M. Cogan (ed.), *In the Lands of Sumer and Akkad: New Studies. A Conference in Honor of JACOB KLEIN on the Occasion of His Eightieth Birthday* (2018) vii-xxviii.

Sumerische Königsliste (3.7.2.a): W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT I/4* (1984) 328-337; J.-J. Glassner, *Chroniques mésopotamiennes* (Paris, 1993) 137-142 (discussion pp. 69-87; 113-117); *ETCSL 2.1.1* (1999); Glassner, *Mesopotamian Chronicles* (2005) 117-127 (discussion pp. 55-70 et 95-99); P. Michalowski, dans: M.W. Chavalas (ed.), *The Ancient Near East* (2006) 81-85; J. Kaula, *CDLP 5* (2016) (édition de WB 1923.444). — Cf. A. Westenholz, *JCS 26* (1974) 154-156; B. Lukács/L. Végso, *AoF 2* (1975) 25-45; R.R. Wilson, *YNER 7* (1977) 72-86; A. Kammenhuber, *Or. 48* (1979) 1-25; M.J. Geller, *Eblaitica 1* (1987) 141-145; C. Wilcke *apud* Hrouda, *Isin III 89-93*; M.-J. Seux, dans Seux et al., *La création et le déluge d'après les textes du Proche-Orient ancien (Supplément au Cahier Evangile 64 [1988])* 45-47; G. Steiner, *ASJ 10* (1988) 129-152; Wilcke dans J. von Ungern-Sternberg/H. Reinau, *Colloquium Rauricum, Band 1, Vergangenheit in mündlicher Überlieferung* (Stuttgart, 1988) 113-140; D.W. Young, *JNES 47* (1988) 123-129; Wilcke, *Mél. Sjöberg 557-571*; C. Vincente, *NABU 1990/11*; J. Klein, *AulOr. 9* (1991) 123-129; W. Heimpel, *ZA 82* (1992) 9 sq.; Steiner, *CRRAI 35* (1988, ed. 1992) 261-279; J.S. Cooper, *HANES 5* (1993) 19 sq.; Rollinger, *Frühformen 227-235*; J.R. Davila, *JNES 54* (1995) 201; Vincente, *ZA 85* (1995) 234-270; Glassner, *Les temps de l'histoire en Mésopotamie*, dans: A. de Pury et al. (rd.), *Israël construit son histoire* (1996) 167-189 (SKL: 170-175); J.S. Cooper, *Suppl. au Dict. de la Bible 72* (1999) 243-245; E. Flückiger-Hawker, *OBO 166* (1999) 41 sq.; Wilcke dans D. Kuhn/H. Stahl (ed.), *Die Gegenwart des Altertums* (2001) 101-116; G.J. Selz, *Die Königsliste als politische Tendenz-Werke*, in: M. Heinz und D. Bonatz (ed.), *Der "Garten Eden" im dritten Jahrtausend [...]* (= *Freiburger Universitätsblätter Heft 156, Juni 2002, 41. Jahrgang*) 21-30; A. Westenholz, dans M.H. Hansen (ed.), *A Comparative Study of Six City-State Cultures* (2002) 32 sq.; M.M. Fritz, *AOAT 307* (2003) 165 sq.; Glassner, dans: N. Grimal et M. Béaud (ed.), *Événement, récit, histoire officielle. L'écriture de l'histoire dans les monarchies antiques* (2003) 70-81; G. Pettinato, *I re di Sumer I* (2003) 49-60; P. Steinkeller, *Mél. Wilcke* (2003) 267-292; D.O. Edzard, *Geschichte Mesopotamiens* (2004) 38-41; Glassner, *Mél. Klein* (2004) 138-141; M. Haul, *CDOG 3* (2004) 240-242 et 245-250; N. Veldhuis, *CM 22* (2004) 76 sq.; H.D. Galter, *AOAT 325* (2005) 276-285; Glassner, *NABU 2005/46*; J. Friberg, *MSCCT 1* (2007) 231-243; J. Klein, *Mél. Sigrist* (2008) 77-91; P. Panitschek, *LUGAL — šarru — basileús [...]* (2008) 457-465; J. Peterson, *AulOr. 26* (2008) 257-262, surtout 257 sq.; C. Mittermayer, *OBO 239* (2009) 90-95; D. Frayne, *CSMS Journal 4* (2009) 39-41; J. Cooper, *JAOS 130* (2010) 330-333; Klein, *CRRAI 53/1* (2010) 1127 sqq.; G. Marchesi, *Mél. Mayer* (2010) 231-248; J.M. Sasson, *Mél. Foster* (2010) 361-373; A.R. George, *CUSAS 17* (2011) 199-205/pl. LXXVIII-LXXXIV n° 96-99 (nouveaux duplicats); G. Marchesi, *MC 14* (2011) 114-118; P. Michalowski, dans: A. Feldherr and G. Hardy (ed.),

The Oxford History of Historical Writing I: Beginnings to AD 600 (2011) 15 sq.; L. Vacin, Šulgi of Ur: Life, Deeds, Ideology and Legacy of a Mesopotamian Ruler as Reflected primarily in Literary Texts (PhD, University of London 2011) 221-227; Y. Cohen, Iraq 74 (2012) 140 sqq.; 6-8, 76 sq., 103 sq.; C. Mittermayer, CRRAI 54 (2012) 313-326; P. Charvát, CRRAI 57 (2015) 75-80; W. Sallaberger/I. Schrakamp, Arcane 3 (2015) 13-22; S.J. Milstein, Tracking the Master Scribe: Revision through Introduction in Biblical and Mesopotamian Literature (2016) 45-50; W. Sommerfeld, Arcane 3 (2015) 271 sq.; T. Janssen, NABU 2016/35; M.R. Bachvarova, dans: M.R. Bachvarova et al. (ed.), The Fall of Cities in the Mediterranean: Commemoration in Literature, Folk-Song, and Liturgy (2016) 39 sq.; N. Brisch Mél. Postgate (2017) 322-330 passim; P. Steinkeller, SANER 15 (2017) 40-42, 44 sq., 58-61, 72-78, 180-183, 192-196, index p. 226; G. Gabriel, AVO 19 (2018) 71-131; P. Michalowski, dans: J. Baines et al. (ed.), Historical Consciousness and the Use of the Past in the Ancient World (2019) 16-24, 30-33; C. Zgoll, Tractatus mythologicus [...] (= Mythological Studies 1 [2019]) 199-204.

(Parodistische?) Königsliste von Lagaš (3.7.2.b): Bottéro/Kramer, Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme 520-525; J.-J. Glassner, Chroniques mésopotamiennes (Paris, 1993) 151-153; ETCSL 2.1.2 (1998-1999); Glassner, Mesopotamian Chronicles (2005) 144-149. — Cf. M.-J. Seux, dans Seux et al., La création et le déluge d'après les textes du Proche-Orient ancien (Supplément au Cahier Evangile 64 [1988]) 41 sq.; B.F. Batto, dans: K.L. Younger et alii (ed.), The Biblical Canon in Comparative Perspective. Scripture in Context IV (1991) 46-48; G. Pettinato, I Sumeri (1991) 189 sq.; Kobayashi, Bulletin of the Orient Museum 10 () 125-151 (cf. Sigrist/alii, CBTBM II 254); J.S. Cooper, Suppl. au Dict. de la Bible 72 (1999) 245; G. Pettinato, Mitologia sumerica (2001) 422-424; id., I re di Sumer I (2003) 62-64; M. Dietrich, MARG 20 (2010) 47-50; B.F. Batto, In the Beginning: Essays on Creation Motifs in the Ancient Near East and the Bible (2013) 71 sq.; Y.S. Chen, The Primeval Flood Catastrophe [...] (2013) 104-106; P. Steinkeller, SANER 15 (2017) 42 sq.

Tummal-'Chronik' (3.7.2.c): SumLet. B: 9 (édition); J.-J. Glassner, Chroniques mésopotamiennes (Paris, 1993) 155 sq.; ETCSL 2.1.3 (1998); J. Oelsner, Mél. Wilcke (2003) 209-224 (édition); G. Pettinato, I re di Sumer I (2003) 60-62; Glassner, Mesopotamian Chronicles (2005) 156-159; P. Michalowski, dans: M.W. Chavalas (ed.), The Ancient Near East (2006) 85-87. — Cf. J.S. Cooper, Suppl. au Dict. de la Bible 72 (1999) 245 sq.; P. Michalowski, CM 35 (2006) 145-165.

Utu-ḫegal-Epos (3.7.2.d): E. Sollberger/J.-R. Kupper, LAPO 3 (1971) 130-132; D.R. Frayne, RIME 2 (1993) 283-293 (édition); ETCSL 2.1.6 (1998); W. Sallaberger, König Utuhengal vertreibt die Gutäer, dans: S. Franke (ed.), Als die Götter Mensch waren (2013) 88-90 et 120. — Cf. G. Pettinato, I Sumeri (1991) 276 sq.; Rollinger, Frühformen 33-36; M. Widell, JAC 15 (2000) 59-65; P. Espak, AOAT 390/4 (2016) 80-86; F. D'Agostino et al., La lingua dei Sumeri (2019) 207-208.

Rätsel (3.7.3.b): M. Civil, AulOr. 5 (1987) 17-37. — Cf. Civil, NABU 1988/43; W.H.Ph. Römer, TUAT III/1 (1990) 44-46; Vanstiphout, Eduba (2004) 52-56; A. Cavigneaux, RIA 11/3-4 (2007) 224.

Sammlungen von 'Sprichwörtern' (3.7.3.c): B. Alster, Assyriological Miscellanies 1 (1980) 33-50 (édition de SP 24); R.S. Falkowitz, The Sumerian Rhetoric Collections. Ph. D.,

Univ. of Pennsylvania, 1980 (édition de SP 3); B. Alster, *Proverbs of Ancient Sumer*. Bethesda, 1997 (édition de toutes les collections); J. Black et al., *ETCSL 6.1-6.2* (2002); B. Alster, *Wisdom of Ancient Sumer* (2005) 391-403 (chapitre 6: Examples of Proverb Collections Used as Literary Source Books); B. Alster, *Sumerian Proverbs in the Schøyen Collection* (= CUSAS 2, 2007) (édition). — Cf. aussi S.N. Kramer, *CRRAI 3* (1954) 75-84; M. Lambert, *RSO 42* (1967) 75-99 et *RSO 45* (1970) 29-58; G.D. Young, *JCS 24* (1971-1972) 132; Kramer, *OECT 5* (1976) 36-41 (Proverbs); J. Bauer, *AoN 15* dans *AoN 9-17* (1980); W.W. Hallo, *JQR 76* (1985) 21-40 (= *WOL 589-605*); id., *Mél. Moran 203-217* (= *WOL 607-623*); W.H.Ph. Römer, *TUAT III/1* (1990) 31-43; B. Alster, *NABU 1992/82*; id., *Proverbium 10* (1993) 1-20; Bauer, *Mél. Hallo 39 sq.*; T.J.H. Krispijn, dans: W.L. Idema et al. (ed.), *"Mijn naam is haas." Dierenverhalten in verschillende culturen* (1993) 132-136; Alster, *CM 6* (1996) 1-21; A. Cavigneaux, *Mél. Limet* (1996) 19-21 (CBS 11945); N. Veldhuis, *JAOS 120* (2000) 383-399; Alster, *Suppl. au Dict. de la Bible 73* (2002) 293-299; Black, J. et alii, *LAS* (2004) 282 sq.; Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 47-52; J. Taylor, *RA 99* (2005) 13-38; Alster/T. Oshima, *Or. 75* (2006) 31-72; Alster, *Or. 75*, 380-389; A. Cavigneaux, *Textes lexicaux et littéraires*, dans C. Proust, *Tablettes mathématiques de Nippur* (2007) 325-356 passim; L. Muntingh, *JSem. 16* (2007) 708-714; Taylor, dans: J. Ebeling and G. Cunningham (ed.) *Analysing Literary Sumerian: Corpus-based Approaches* (London-Oakville: Equinox Publishing Ltd 2007) 273-315; M. Krebernik, *TMH 8* (2008) 79-82; S. Seminara, *Or. 78* (2009) 379-393; E. Frahm, *Mél. Foster* (2010) 155-184; G.J. Selz, dans: P. Charvát and P.M. Vlcková (ed.), *Who Was King? Who Was Not King [...]* (2010) 8-13; S. Seminara, *Mél. Mayer* (2010) 369-374; B. Alster, *PIHANS 118* (2011) 9-27; J. Peterson, *BPOA 9* (2011) 243-299; N. Wasserman, *RIA 13/1-2* (2011) 19-23 passim; A. Cavigneaux, *OBO 256* (2012) 84 sq.; A. Gadotti, dans M.W. Chavalas (ed.), *Women in the Ancient Near East* (2014) 60-62 et 68-70; J. Klein, *BaBi 8*. (2014) 271-304; J. Fechner, *Moral Concepts within the Sumerian-Akkadian Proverbial Literature: Origins, Developments and Tendencies*, dans: M-S. Ortola/G. Achard-Bayle (ed.), *Concepts éthiques et moraux: approches multiculturelles et interdisciplinaires. Sémantique des énoncés parémiques* (2015) 17-60, surtout 30-42; J. Klein/N. Samet, *Mél. Hurowitz* (2015) 295-321; M. Viano, *The Reception of Sumerian Literature in the Western Periphery* (2016) 63-65 et 103 sq.; G. Konstantopoulos, *Kaskal 14* (2017) 125-140; C.J. Crisostomo, *SANER 22* (2019) 70-73; id., *Kaskal 16* (2019) 141-157.

Early Dynastic Proverb Coll. 1: Alster, *AfO 38-39* (1991/1992) 1-51 (édition). — Cf. aussi J. Klein, *Mél. Wilcke* (2003) 135-149; J. Fechner, *Moral Concepts within the Sumerian-Akkadian Proverbial Literature: Origins, Developments and Tendencies*, dans: M-S. Ortola/G. Achard-Bayle (ed.), *Concepts éthiques et moraux: approches multiculturelles et interdisciplinaires. Sémantique des énoncés parémiques* (2015) 24-28.

Beschwörungen (3.8.1): M. Krebernik, *Die Beschwörungen aus Fara und Ebla. Untersuchungen zur ältesten keilschriftlichen Beschwörungsliteratur* (= *TSO 2*, 1984); P. Michalowski, *QdS 18* (1992) 305-326; G. Cunningham, *'Deliver me from Evil' [...]*, *StPohl SM 17*, Roma 1997; *Magic in the Ancient Near East*, *SEL 15* (1998); T. Abush/K. van der Toorn (ed.), *Mesopotamian Magic [...]* (= *AMD 1*, 1999); M.J. Geller, *Suppl. au Dict. de la Bible 73* (2002) 269-283; J.J.A van Dijk/M.J. Geller, *TMH 6* (2003); N. Rudik, *Die Entwicklung der keilschriftlichen sumerischen Beschwörungsliteratur von den Anfängen bis zur Ur III-Zeit. Dissertation zur Erlangung des akademischen Grades Doctor philosophiae*,

Universität Jena 2111 (<http://www.db-thueringen.de/servlets/DerivateServlet/Derivate-32004/Diss/DoktorarbeitRudik.pdf>); A.R. George, CUSAS 32 (2016); A. Johandi, *The God Asar/Asalluḫi in the Early Mesopotamian Pantheon* (Dissertationes Theologiae Universitatis Tartuensis 37, 2019) passim.

Liebeszauber (3.8.2): Nouvelle traduction de ZA 56 (1964) 113-129 par W.H.Ph. Römer, TUAT II/2 (1987) 208-210; M.J. Geller, CRRAI 47 (2002) 129 sq. et 135-139 (nouvelle édition).

Satiren (3.9): Pour Ugubi, cf. aussi Th. Jacobsen, OIP 98 (1990) 105 sq. et n. 25 et ETCSL 3.3.07 (2005).

Elegie auf den Tod des Nannamu (3.10.a) **und Elegie auf den Tod des Nawirtum** (3.10.b): ETCSL 5.5.2 (1998-1999) et 5.5.3 (1998-2000); G. Pettinato, *Mitologia sumerica* (2001) 477-491; Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 258-263 (3.10.a). — Cf. T. Kuwabara, *The Netherworld in Sumerian-Akkadian Literature* (Ph. D., Univ. of California at Berkeley, 1991) 108-114; A.C. Cohen, AMD 7 (2005) 50 sq.; A. Löhnert, dans: C. Felli (ed.), *How to Cope with Death: Mourning and Funerary Practices in the Ancient Near East. Proceedings of the International Workshop Firenze, 5th-6th December 2013* (2016) 49-66.

Die drei Freunde aus Adab (3.10.c): B.R. Foster, ANES 6 (1974) 70-72 (édition); B. Alster, JCS 43-45 (1991-1993) 27-38 (édition); ETCSL 5.6.5 (1999); Alster, *Wisdom* (2005) 373-383 (édition). — Cf. A. Cavigneaux, ASJ 9 (1987) 51 sq.; W.G. Lambert, NABU 1995/2; Alster, dans: K. Eksell/L. Feldt (ed.), *Readings in Eastern Mediterranean Literatures* (2006) 72-75; Gadotti, *Sumerian wisdom literature* 65 sq., 67 sq., 71-73; M. Viano, *The Reception of Sumerian Literature in the Western Periphery* (2016) 61 sq.

"Home of the Fish" (3.10.d): ETCSL 5.9.1 (1999); Black et alii, LAS 240-244; Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 104-111. — Cf. H.L.J. Vanstiphout, OLA 13 (1982) 311-319; Peterson, *Faunal Conception* 488-495; A. Gadotti/A. Kleinerman, NABU 2017/39.

Liebeslieder (3.10.e): 27 compositions considérées comme des "love songs"³ ont été éditées en dernier lieu par Y. Sefati, *Love Songs in Sumerian Literature* [...], Ramat-Gan 1998; cf. également Alster, RA 79 (1985) 127-159 et *Mél. Hallo* 15-27 (riche bibliographie pp. 26 sq.; ajouter J.G. Westenholz, CRRAI 38 [1991, ed. 1992] 381-387); ETCSL 4.08./... (1998-1999). — J.S. Cooper, CM 7 (1997) 85-97; V. Haas, *Babylonischer Liebesgarten* [...], München 1999; Kramer/Molina, *El Matrimonio Sagrado* passim; M.M. Fritz, AOAT 307 (2003) 69-96; P. Lapinkivi, SAAS 15 (2004) 30-50 passim; P. Mander, *Canti sumerici d'amore e morte* (Testi del Vicino Oriente antico 2/8, 2005); Fritz, dans: B. Heininger (ed.), *An den Schwellen des Lebens. Zur Geschlechterdifferenz in Ritualen des Übergangs* (2008) 27-87; Y. Sefati/J. Klein, *Two Dumuzi-Inanna Love Songs: Dumuzi-Inanna Q and an Unidentified Song*, *Mél. Skaist* (2012) 309-334; Broekema, *Inanna* (2013) 297-309; L.M. Pryke, *Ishtar: Gods and Heroes of the Ancient World* (2017) 31-59 passim.

Liebeslied Šulgis (3.10.e 1): ETCSL 2.4.2.26 (2000).

³ Comp. aussi Å.W. Sjöberg, JCS 29 (1977) 16-27 et 39-43 n° 5; CT 58 12-14, 15 // 16 et 22; B. Alster, ASJ 14 (1992) 1-46.

Liebeslied Šū-Sins (3.10.e 2): Nouvelles éditions: Alster, RA 79 138-142; Sefati, Love Songs 344-352; Th. Jacobsen, Mél. Pope 57-60; ETCSL 2.4.4.1 (1999). — Nouvelles traductions: Castellino, TSA 191-193; Kramer/Bottéro, Mariage sacré 112-114; Jacobsen, The Harps that once ... 95 sq.; P. Mander, Canti sumerici d'amore e morte (Testi del Vicino Oriente antico 2/8, 2005) 144-146; Attinger, TTS (2010, actualisé en 2017) (B); C. Halton/S. Svärd, Women's Writing of Ancient Mesopotamia: An Anthology of the Earliest Female Authors (2018) 105-110 (A et B). — Cf. Jacobsen, JCS 7 (1953) 46 sq. (= TIT 184-186); E. Sollberger, JCS 30 (1978) 99 sq.; D.R. Frayne, BiOr. 42 (1985) 9 sq.; M. Widell, JNES 70 (2011) 289-302.

Die Botschaft des Ludingira an seine Mutter (3.10.f): S.N. Kramer, BiMes. 4 (1976) 19-21; T.R. Kämmerer, AOAT 251 (1998) 13 sq. et 164-169; ETCSL 5.5.1 (2000); Black et alii, LAS 190-192; Vanstiphout, Eduba (2004) 253-258; D. Arnaud, AulOr-S 23 (2007) 179-185 n° 50 (version d'Ugarit); A. Gadotti, Mél. Owen (2010) 115-129 (édition). — Cf. W. Heimpel, StPohl 2 (1968) 60-64; J.S. Cooper, JBL 90 (1971) 157-162; J. van Dijk dans J.P. Asmussen/*alii* (ed.), Handbuch der Religionsgeschichte I (Göttingen, 1971) 493 sq.; Wilcke, UT 151 sq.; M. Stol, Women in Ancient Near East (2016) 157; M. Viano, The Reception of Sumerian Literature in the Western Periphery (2016) 256-265.

Lugal-anne-mundu (3.10.g): Cf. D.O. Edzard, RIA 7, 1/2 (1987) 114 s.v. Lugal-anne-mundu (bibl.); Yang Zhi, JAC 4 (1989) 55-60.

Nanše und die Vögel (3.10.h): ETCSL 4.4.3 (2000); N. Veldhuis, CM 22 (2004) 115-142 (édition).

Ninurta und die Schildkröte (3.10.i): Bottéro/Kramer, Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme 418-424; ETCSL 1.6.3 (1998); B. Alster, CM 35 (2006) 13-36 (édition); L. Feldt, dans: K. Eksell/L. Feldt (ed.), Readings in Eastern Mediterranean Literatures (2006) 83-127 (éd.). — Cf. Kramer/Maier, Myths of Enki 84-86; Penglase, Greek Myths 61 sq.; Wagensonner, Götterreisen (2005) 97-99; Peterson, Faunal Conception 456-467 (ll. 36-46); J.-D. Forest, Mém. Bottéro (2009) 47-53 *passim*.

Ochsenpflügerlied (3.10.j): ETCSL 5.5.5 (1999). — Cf. A. Livingstone, ZA 70 (1980) 55-57.

Ur-Nammus Tod (3.10.k): C. Wilcke, Urnammu's Tod [...] (ms. non publié); S.N. Kramer, Mél. Takahito Mikasa 193-214 (édition); E. Flückiger-Hawker, OBO 166 (1999) 93-182 (édition); ETCSL 2.4.1.1 (1999-2000); Black et alii, LAS 56-62. — Cf. T. Kuwabara, The Netherworld in Sumerian-Akkadian Literature (Ph. D., Univ. of California at Berkeley, 1991) 114-119; G. Pettinato, I Sumeri (1991) 288 sq.; Rollinger, Frühformen 60-63; D. Katz, The Image of the Netherworld in the Sumerian Sources (2003) *passim*, surtout 329-336 (index des lignes discutées p. 480); B. Studevent-Hickman, dans: M.W. Chavalas (ed.), The Ancient Near East (2006) 61-65; P. Michalowski, dans: A. Feldherr and G. Hardy (ed.), The Oxford History of Historical Writing I: Beginnings to AD 600 (2011) 17 sq.; Jordanova, A., Untersuchungen zur Gestalt einer Unterweltsgöttin: Ereškigal nach den sumerischen und akkadischen Quellentexten. Dissertation zur Erlangung des akademischen Grades Doctor Philosophiae (Dr. phil.), Universität Leipzig (2015) 370-374; P. Steinkeller, CRRAI 60

(2017) 15 sq. avec n. 55; M.T. Sharlach, *SANER* 18 (2017) 176 sq.; C. Halton/S. Svärd, *Women's Writing of Ancient Mesopotamia: An Anthology of the Earliest Female Authors* (2018) 110-115 (ll. 1-216); E.S. Gerstenberger, *Theologie des Lobens in sumerischen Hymnen* (= *ORA* 28, 2018) 111 sq.

Wiegenlied (3.10.1): *ETCSL* 2.4.2.14 (2000); Vanstiphout, *Eduba* (2004) 265-270; K. Volk, dans K. Volk (ed.), *Erzählungen aus dem Land Sumer* (2015) 83-88 et 418 sq.; C. Halton/S. Svärd, *Women's Writing of Ancient Mesopotamia: An Anthology of the Earliest Female Authors* (2018) 102-105. — Cf. B. Alster, *RA* 65 (1971) 170 sq.

